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优化生态空间网络以实现碳封存和气候恢复：巴基斯坦旁遮普
省塔尔沙漠生态修复研究

Optimizing Ecological Spatial Networks for Carbon Sequestration and Climate
Resilience: A Study of Ecological Restoration in the Thal Desert in Punjab, Pakistan

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Optimizing Ecological Spatial Networks for Carbon Sequestration and Climate Resilience: A Study of Ecological Restoration in the Thal Desert in Punjab, Pakistan

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Abstract

Achieving carbon neutrality is a critical global objective in the effort to mitigate climate change, requiring a dual approach of reducing carbon emissions and enhancing carbon sequestration within terrestrial ecosystems. Desert ecosystems, such as the Thal Desert in Punjab Province, Pakistan, are particularly vulnerable to severe environmental degradation, desertification, and significant vegetation loss, which severely diminish their ability to function as effective carbon sinks. This study investigates how optimizing ecological spatial networks (ESNs) can enhance carbon sequestration and contribute to achieving carbon neutrality in this ecologically fragile region. Advanced spatial modeling techniques were employed to optimize ESNs by improving the connectivity and structure of fragmented ecological patches. The Minimum Cumulative Resistance (MCR) model was used to identify and create ecological corridors, facilitating species migration and enabling ecological flows necessary for ecosystem stability and biodiversity conservation. Network topology analyses were conducted using Gephi software to quantify key metrics such as node connectivity, degree centrality, betweenness centrality, and clustering coefficient, which provide insights into the ecological importance and network integrity of habitat patches. Furthermore, the Energy Flow and Connectivity Topology (EFCT) model was utilized to optimize the ESN structure, focusing on maximizing carbon sequestration potential alongside ecological connectivity.

The study identified critical ecological source patches (ESPs) and classified them into five distinct functional communities, revealing marked spatial variability in ecological functions and connectivity across the desert landscape. By integrating 27 new ecological patches and establishing 51 new ecological corridors, the optimized network increased the overall carbon sequestration capacity of the Thal Desert by approximately 14.97%. Forest and wetland ecosystems emerged as the principal contributors to carbon storage, underscoring the necessity to prioritize their restoration. The optimized ecological networks also demonstrated enhanced resilience and stability in the face of environmental disturbances such as climate variability and human activities, compared to the original, fragmented networks. These findings underscore the significance of optimizing ecological spatial networks to restore connectivity among fragmented habitats as an effective strategy for enhancing carbon sequestration, biodiversity, and ecosystem resilience in arid environments. Restoration measures such as reforestation, afforestation, and the improvement of soil water and nutrient availability are essential for fostering vegetation recovery and sustaining long-term ecosystem function. This research provides valuable insights and practical guidance for desert ecosystem restoration

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and climate change mitigation, with implications extending beyond the Thal Desert to other arid and semi-arid regions globally that face similar challenges of desertification and land degradation.

Keywords: Ecological Spatial Network (ESN), EFCT Model, Topological Indicator, Carbon Neutrality, Thal Desert

优化生态空间网络以实现碳封存和气候恢复：巴基斯坦旁遮普省 塔尔沙漠生态修复研究

摘要

实现碳中和是全球应对气候变化的重要目标，既需要减少碳排放，也需要提升陆地生态系统中的碳汇能力。沙漠生态系统如巴基斯坦旁遮普省的塔尔沙漠，因环境恶化、沙漠化和植被大量丧失，碳汇功能受到严重削弱。本研究探讨通过优化生态空间网络（ESNs）提高该脆弱生态区域碳封存能力，实现碳中和的可行路径。本研究采用先进的空间建模技术，通过改善分散生态斑块的结构与连通性，优化生态空间网络。运用最小累积阻力（MCR）模型识别并构建生态廊道，促进物种迁移及生态流动，维持生态系统稳定性和生物多样性保护。通过 Gephi 软件分析生态网络拓扑特征，包括节点连通性、度中心性、介数中心性和聚类系数，揭示栖息地斑块的重要性及网络完整性。同时，采用能量流与连通拓扑（EFCT）模型优化生态空间网络结构，聚焦于提升碳封存潜力及生态连通性。

研究识别出关键生态源斑块（ESPs），并将其划分为五个功能性群落，展示出沙漠生态功能与连通性存在显著空间差异。通过新增 27 个生态斑块和 51 条生态廊道，优化后的网络使塔尔沙漠整体碳封存能力提升约 14.97%。森林和湿地生态系统成为碳存储的主要贡献者，强调其修复的重要性。优化后的生态网络在面对气候变化和人类活动等环境扰动时表现出更强的韧性和稳定性，优于原有分散的网络结构。研究结果强调，优化生态空间网络以恢复碎片化栖息地间连通性，是提升干旱环境碳封存、生物多样性和生态系统韧性的有效策略。重新造林、植树造林及改善土壤水分和养分状况等生态恢复措施，对于促进植被恢复和维持生态系统长期功能至关重要。本研究为沙漠生态系统恢复与气候变化缓解提供了重要的理论和实践指导，其成果不仅适用于塔尔沙漠，也对面临类似沙漠化和土地退化问题的全球干旱半干旱地区具有广泛意义。

关键词：生态空间网络（ESN）、EFCT 模型、拓扑指标、碳中和、塔尔沙漠

Contents	
Abstract.....	I
摘要.....	II
Chapter-I.....	1
1 Introduction.....	1
1.1 Research background and significance.....	1
1.2 Related theories and Research progress.....	3
1.2.1 Progress in theoretical research on desertification.....	3
1.2.2 Ecological Networks: A Strategy for Restoration.....	5
1.2.3 Enhancing Ecological Processes Through Spatial Optimization.....	6
1.2.4 Research Objectives.....	7
Chapter-II.....	9
2 Review of Literature.....	9
2.1 Landscape Spatial Structure and Carbon Neutrality.....	9
2.3 Spatial Structure and Biodiversity Conservation.....	13
2.6 Carbon Fingerprint and Reduction Strategies.....	17
2.8 Ecological Network in Arid and Semi-Arid Environments.....	24
Chapter-III.....	27
3 Overview of study area and research content.....	27
3.1 Overview of the Study Area.....	27
3.1.1 Geographical Location.....	27
3.1.2. Topographic and Geomorphic Features.....	28
3.1.3. Climate and Hydrological Characteristics.....	28
3.1.4. Vegetation Distribution Characteristics.....	28
3.1.5 Socioeconomic characteristics.....	28
3.2 Data Source and Processing.....	30
3.2.1 Data Sources.....	31
3.2.3 Research Content.....	34
3.2.4 Technological Roadmap.....	34
Chapter-IV.....	36
4. Research Methods.....	36
4.1 Networks.....	36
4.1.1 Construction of Ecological Spatial Network.....	36

4.1.2	Fundamentals of Ecological Spatial Networks	36
4.1.3	Ecological Source Identification.....	37
4.2	Construction of an Ecological Corridor	39
4.2.1	Minimum Cumulative Resistance (MCR) Model for Corridor Identification.....	40
4.2.1.2	Resistance surfaces	40
4.2.2	Least-Cost Path Analysis for Corridor Mapping	40
4.2.3	Resistance Surface and Factor Selection	41
4.3	Topological Indicators for Optimizing Spatial Network.....	43
4.3.1	Degree	43
4.3.2	Clustering coefficient.....	43
4.3.3	Betweenness.....	44
4.3.4	Ecological Significance of Betweenness Centrality	44
4.3.5	Coreness.....	44
4.4	Ecological Network Gravity	45
4.4.1	Theoretical Basis of the Ecological Gravity Model.....	45
4.4.2	Modification of the Gravity Model for Desert Ecosystems.....	45
4.4.3	Application of Ecological Gravity for Network Optimization	46
4.4.4	Significance of Ecological Gravity Model in Desert Ecosystems	46
4.5	EFCT optimization model.....	46
4.5.1	Core Components of the EFCT Model	46
4.5.4	Visualization and Mapping of EFCT Optimization Outputs	48
4.5.5	Application of EFCT Model in Desert Ecosystems	48
4.5.6	Expected Benefits and Implications of the EFCT Model	48
4.6	Calculating Carbon Sequestration Accuracy	49
4.6.1	Method for Calculating Carbon Sequestration	49
4.7	Robustness of Ecological Spatial Network.....	51
4.7.1	Key Challenges Affecting ESN Robustness	51
4.7.2	Evaluating the Robustness of the Ecological Spatial Network.....	51
4.7.3	Network Vulnerability to Disturbances.....	52
4.7.4	Methodology for ESN Robustness Analysis.....	52
4.7.5	Impact of Network Disturbances on Ecological Stability.....	52
4.7.6	Strategies to Improve Network Robustness	53
4.7.7	Summary of this chapter	53

Chapter-V	55
5. Results.....	55
5.1 Extraction and Analysis of Ecological Spatial Network.....	55
5.1.1 Screening of Ecological Sources	55
5.1.2 Analyzing Ecological MCR Surface.....	57
5.2 Ecological Spatial Network in the Thal Desert.....	58
5.2.1 Ecological Source and Corridor Distribution	59
5.3.3 Closeness Centrality.....	62
5.3.4 Betweenness Centrality.....	62
5.3.5 Eigenvector Centrality	62
5.3.6 Network Optimization and Improvements.....	62
1 5.4 The Impact of Evaluation on Optimization	64
5.4.1 Optimization and Spatial Structure Evaluation.....	64
5.4.2 Results of Optimization	65
5.5 Carbon Sink Capacity and Robustness	65
5.5.1 Analyzing and Comparison of Various Optimization Approaches	66
5.5.2 Assessing Carbon Sink vs. Source.....	68
5.5.3 Carbon Sink Assessment Before and After Optimization.....	69
5.5.4 Role of Ecological Patches in Carbon Sequestration.....	70
5.5.5 Comparison Between Carbon Sinks and Sources.....	71
5.6 Connection Resilience under Attacks	73
5.6.1 Impact of Optimization on Robustness.....	73
5.6.1 Node-Level Analysis and Recovery Resilience.....	74
5.7 Summary of this chapter	75
Chapter-VI	77
6 Discussion	77
Chapter-VII.....	80
7 Conclusion	80
7.1 Research Outlook.....	80
8. References.....	82
Personal Profile.....	93
Instructor Profile	94
Acknowledgments.....	97

Figure 3.1 1 Overview of the study area.....	30
Figure 3.2 1 The datasets are derived from multiple sources of remote sensing and geospatial information.....	30
Figure 3.2.4 1 The technical roadmap in the first phase of the study was to identify ecological source areas that are important for the conservation of biodiversity and ecosystem services.	35
Figure 4.5.6 1 Conceptual Flow Chart illustrating the optimization model for EFCT	49
Figure 5.1.1.3 1 Construction of ecological source patches (a) and ecological spatial network (b) in the Thal Desert (a) Ecological source patches	56
Figure 5.1.2.3 1 Basement resistivity and areas of minimum cumulative resistivity (MCR) in the Thal Desert (a) Basement resistivity map. (b) Minimum cumulative resistivity (MCR) surface	58
<i>Figure 5.3.1 1 Ecological Spatial Network (ESN) of the Thal Desert, illustrating nodes with varying centrality. Blue nodes (1) represent high centrality, red nodes (2) indicate medium centrality, green nodes (3), and other colors (4) represent lower centrality. The node size corresponds to connectivity, with nodes having higher degrees being more central to the network.....</i>	<i>61</i>
<i>Figure 5.3.6 1 Topological analysis of the Thal Desert eco-spatial network, showing the distribution of (a) node degrees, (b) clustering coefficients, (c) proximity centrality, (d) betweenness centrality, and (e) eigenvector centrality. Key nodes (nodes 0, 9, 55, and 76) are crucial for network connectivity and ecosystem stability</i>	<i>63</i>
Figure 5.4.1 1 Comparison of unoptimized (left) and optimized (right) landscape structures in the Thal Desert, showing improved connectivity with added nodes (green) and corridors (blue).....	65
<i>Figure 5.5 1 Optimization of the Ecological Spatial Network in the Thal Desert, showing unoptimized (a) and optimized (b) landscape structures with enhanced connectivity and resilience.</i>	<i>66</i>
Figure 5.5.1.2 1 Optimization methods in the Thal Desert ESN. (a) Edge addition enhances connectivity (pink corridors), with limited carbon storage impact. (b) The stepping stone	

technique adds patches (pink) to bridge gaps, without significantly affecting carbon sequestration.68

Figure 5.5.2 1 Comparison of carbon sequestration before (red) and after (green) ESN optimization in the Thal Desert, showing increased carbon storage capacity.69

Figure 5.5.4 1 Carbon sequestration in the Thal Desert after ESN optimization, showing improved patches and added carbon sinks, enhancing ecological connectivity and resilience.71

Figure 5.5.5 1 Comparison of the Thal Desert eco-spatial network before and after optimization, showing added nodes and expanded corridors, increasing carbon sequestration by 14.97%.73

Figure 5.6.1 1 Comparison of network resilience before and after optimization, showing slower declines in connection and attack resilience in the optimized network.75

Table 3.2.1 1 Data source in the Thal Desert area in Punjab, Pakistan.....	31
Table 4.1.3.2 1 Criteria for evaluating ecological patches and their target species.	38
Table 4.2.3 1 Resistance Factors and Weights Assigned in MCR Model.....	41
Table 4.6.1.2 1 Carbon sequestration coefficient for various land use categories.	50
Table 5.5.3 1 Carbon sink in Thal Desert, Punjab, Pakistan, before and after ESN optimization.	70
Table 5.5.5 1 Energy Use and Emissions of Carbon (C) Sink in the Thal Desert, Pakistan...	72

Chapter-I

1 Introduction

1.1 Research background and significance

Greenhouse gas emissions have risen at an alarming rate over the past century, leading to unprecedented global temperature increases. Rising temperatures have had profound impacts on the environment, causing the melting of polar ice caps, a subsequent rise in sea levels, and a significant increase in the frequency and intensity of extreme weather events such as hurricanes, floods, and droughts ^[1, 2]. These environmental changes pose a major threat to humans and ecosystems, with vulnerable populations in coastal areas, low-lying islands, and arid regions particularly at risk. The impacts of these changes are not limited to the natural environment but also have far-reaching socioeconomic consequences. For example, rising sea levels threaten the livelihoods of millions of people in coastal areas, forcing them to adapt to changing land use patterns or face displacement ^[3]. In addition, extreme weather events such as prolonged droughts, severe storms, and heat waves can undermine agricultural productivity, exacerbate water scarcity, and increase the risk of food insecurity, especially in already vulnerable regions. As these environmental changes continue, there is a growing need for more effective and innovative strategies to mitigate the effects of climate change. To address these challenges, international organizations, governments, and researchers have emphasized the importance of reducing greenhouse gas emissions through various means, including promoting carbon neutrality. Strategies such as afforestation, reforestation, and sustainable land management practices are gaining attention as ways to enhance carbon sequestration and restore ecosystems that are critical to the health of the Earth ^[4]. Carbon neutrality refers to achieving a balance between the amount of carbon emitted into the atmosphere and the amount of carbon removed, primarily through natural processes such as plant growth and soil carbon storage.

However, the challenges of climate change mitigation are multifaceted and require a deep understanding of the complex relationships between the atmosphere, land, and organisms. For example, vegetation plays an important role in the carbon cycle, acting as both a carbon sink and a source of carbon emissions ^[5]. However, some ecosystems, such as deserts, are particularly vulnerable to climate change, and desertification exacerbates the degradation of

already fragile landscapes ^[6]. In regions such as the Thal Desert, the interaction between drought, extreme heat, and land degradation creates a vicious cycle that further reduces the region's carbon sequestration capacity and threatens biodiversity and human well-being ^[7]. Desert ecosystems are not only characterized by high temperatures and drought, but also face challenges such as nutrient loss, reduced soil moisture, and the spread of invasive species. These factors make them particularly vulnerable to climate change, but they also provide unique opportunities for ecological restoration and sustainable land management. Implementing effective restoration measures, such as increasing vegetation cover or improving soil health, can increase the carbon sequestration capacity of these ecosystems and mitigate the broader impacts of climate change. To address these challenges, an integrated approach is needed that combines ecological restoration, carbon sequestration, and sustainable land management practices. In particular, ecological network optimization—a concept that focuses on improving landscape connectivity and ecological resilience—is gaining increasing attention as a key strategy for improving ecosystem services and addressing climate change. Ecological networks facilitate the flow of energy, materials, and species across fragmented landscapes, thereby promoting biodiversity and improving ecosystem stability. In desert regions, establishing ecological corridors and restoring fragmented habitats are essential to improving the overall resilience of landscapes and ensuring that ecosystems can withstand increasing climate change pressures ^[8].

This study aims to investigate the role of ecological networks in improving carbon sequestration and resilience in the Thal Desert, a region that is particularly vulnerable to heat, drought, and desertification. Focusing on ecological restoration, landscape connectivity, and carbon neutrality, this study aims to develop a more sustainable approach to managing desert ecosystems in the context of ongoing climate change. In response to the escalating global climate crisis, the concept of "carbon neutrality" has received widespread attention and has become a key strategy for mitigating climate change. Carbon neutrality is the process of balancing greenhouse gas emissions to achieve net zero emissions through an equal amount of carbon sequestration or offset activities. This goal is critical to combating global warming, as uncontrolled emissions lead to continued increases in global temperatures. This has led to more frequent and severe climate disasters such as heat waves, floods, and droughts. Key strategies to achieve carbon neutrality include reducing the use of fossil fuels, promoting renewable

energy, and strengthening natural processes that capture and store carbon, such as reforestation and reforestation.^[9, 10]

Reforestation and afforestation are particularly important because they take advantage of the natural carbon sequestration capacity of forests. Trees absorb carbon dioxide from the atmosphere during photosynthesis and store much of the carbon in their biomass and soil. In this way, they act as long-term carbon sinks. This process not only mitigates climate change by removing carbon from the atmosphere, but also helps improve soil health, biodiversity, and overall ecosystem resilience. As human activities continue to impact the environment, understanding how to use ecosystems to increase carbon sequestration is critical to achieving global climate goals. Achieving CO₂ neutrality requires more than just increasing CO₂ storage capacity. It also requires managing the timing of emissions and carbon capture. An important milestone in this process is reaching what is known as "peak carbon." This concept refers to the point at which greenhouse gas emissions reach a maximum level and then begin to decline, ultimately resulting in a reduction in the amount of carbon in the global atmosphere. Limiting carbon emissions is essential to slowing the rate of global warming and limiting its potentially devastating effects on ecosystems and human societies.^[11-13]

Vegetation plays an important role in carbon capture and storage. Vegetation acts as a natural carbon sink, absorbing carbon dioxide during photosynthesis and storing it in biomass and soil. After CO₂ emissions peak, emission reductions can be achieved through technological innovation, stricter regulation and global cooperation to ensure the transition to a sustainable, low-carbon future. The role of vegetation in mitigating climate change is fundamental to the concept of carbon neutrality. Vegetation acts as a natural carbon sink: during photosynthesis, it absorbs carbon dioxide from the atmosphere and stores it in plant biomass and the surrounding soil. Forests, grasslands, wetlands and other vegetated ecosystems make an important contribution to the global carbon cycle by capturing large amounts of carbon. The effectiveness of these ecosystems in sequestering carbon is affected by a variety of factors, including species composition, vegetation density and environmental conditions. Forest ecosystems are known for their high carbon storage potential, and mature forests are important carbon sinks. Conversely, disturbances such as deforestation and forest degradation reduce the ability of these ecosystems to store carbon. This allows the stored carbon to be released back into the atmosphere, further exacerbating climate change^[14]. The effectiveness of the process is

influenced by factors such as species composition, vegetation density and environmental conditions.

1.2 Related theories and Research progress

1.2.1 Progress in theoretical research on desertification

Desertification originated in the 1920s and 1930s when foresters in Britain and France worried that continued drought and overgrazing would cause crops and pastures to become desert-like [15]. In 1949, French forest ecologists first used the term to refer to the soil degradation process in tropical humid areas [16]. In 1973, the Sahel region on the southern edge of the Sahara Desert experienced uninterrupted drought, causing much of the region to degrade. The scope and intensity of desertification have increased, affecting more than 900 million people in more than 100 countries around the world. Its scope is still increasing, posing a huge threat to people's lives and property safety [17]. Agricultural production is one of the main production and management activities in desert areas. 44% of the world's arable land is dry land. Desertification will reduce the natural productivity of the land and affect agricultural development [18]. Soil wind erosion is the main form of desertification. During the wind erosion process, the topsoil particles are blown away, resulting in coarsening of the soil texture, reduced soil water holding capacity, reduced fertility, and reduced agricultural production [19]. Zhao et al. (2006) conducted field experiments on farmland in the Horqin Sandy Land. The results showed that crop growth was severely inhibited by wind erosion, and soil physical and chemical properties declined to varying degrees. [20] explored the impact of desertification on farmland in Rajasthan, India. The results showed that the rapid population growth has led to the continuous outward expansion of agricultural activities, the gradual conversion of forest areas into agricultural land, and the reduction of vegetation cover, resulting in different degrees of changes in productivity, soil organic carbon, and soil nutrients in the region. Against this background, in 1977 the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) Desertification will also lead to a decrease in ecosystem biodiversity. Studied the habitats of lizard communities with different desertification degrees in the Ordos region. The results showed that with the increase in desertification degree, UNEP held a World Conference on Desertification in Kenya and formally proposed a definition of desertification, believing that desertification is the richness of lizard communities in the habitat, the Shannon-Weiner diversity index, the Pirro evenness index, and the Simpson diversity index showed a significant downward trend. In addition, desertification can also directly or indirectly affect the social economy. However,

these broad definitions do not limit desertification to geographical or climatic factors, nor do they explain the processes and causes involved, leading to long-standing international debate on the definition of desertification. [21] showed that desertification is threatening Iraq's food security and affecting its socio-economic development. The continuous migration of rural populations to cities has led to the spread of poverty and an increase in unemployment. UNEP adjusted the definition of desertification, defining it as the result of bad human behavior. Later, the United Nations pointed out at the Rio de Janeiro Conference in 1992 that climate change is also a key factor causing desertification.

Desert ecosystems, such as the Thal Desert in Pakistan's Punjab province, face unique challenges when it comes to carbon sequestration. These ecosystems are characterized by extreme temperatures, limited rainfall, and poor soil quality, all of which make them extremely vulnerable to the impacts of climate change. In addition to the natural factors that contribute to desertification, human activities such as deforestation, unsustainable agricultural practices, and overgrazing further degrade these fragile environments. The degradation of desert ecosystems leads to a range of negative consequences, including atmospheric drying, soil nutrient depletion, and water scarcity. As vegetation cover decreases, land becomes increasingly susceptible to wind erosion, which exacerbates the desertification process and leads to a loss of carbon storage capacity [22, 23]. Desertification not only reduces the ability of these ecosystems to capture and store carbon, it also threatens biodiversity, agricultural productivity, and the livelihoods of local communities.

The Thal Desert is an example of such a fragile landscape. Located in northern Pakistan, the region is characterized by dryness and low rainfall, and the vegetation consists mainly of drought-tolerant species and sparse shrubs. Despite the harsh conditions, the Thal Desert has the potential for ecological restoration and carbon sequestration if managed properly. Restoration efforts such as afforestation and reforestation have the potential to increase the desert's carbon uptake capacity and mitigate some of the effects of desertification. By increasing vegetation cover and improving soil quality, the region's ability to absorb carbon can be increased and provide ecosystem services such as water retention and soil stabilization. However, these efforts require a deep understanding of the region's ecological processes and the factors that influence vegetation growth and carbon storage. This study focuses on the impacts of heat and drought on desert ecosystems, specifically studying the response of the Thal Desert to climate change and anthropogenic degradation. This study aims to investigate how changes in temperature and precipitation patterns caused by climate change affect

vegetation health and its carbon sequestration capacity. By understanding the dynamics of carbon sequestration in desert ecosystems under climate change conditions, this study will provide valuable insights into the development of sustainable land management and climate change mitigation strategies in arid regions [24].

Desertification, if left unchecked, may result in irreversible loss of agricultural land, threatening food security, biodiversity, and the livelihoods of communities that rely on these ecosystems.[25]. Restoring degraded desert landscapes is essential to halting and reversing these trends. Increasing vegetation cover through afforestation and reforestation not only absorbs carbon from the atmosphere, but also improves soil health, restores ecological balance and mitigates the effects of climate change. The success of such restoration efforts is closely linked to the availability of soil water and nutrients. These are determined by the spatial structure of the landscape. Optimizing these factors is essential to promote strong plant growth and maximize carbon sequestration potential.[26-28]. The ability to improve vegetation or optimize plant growth is related to the external environment and the water and nutrient content of the soil. The movement of these substances is determined by the spatial structure of the landscape.[29, 30]

In recent decades, great progress has been made in the study of climate change, carbon sinks and ecological restoration. Faced with severe challenges such as global temperature rise, land degradation and frequent extreme weather events, many studies have focused on understanding the dynamics of desert ecosystems, the response of vegetation to climate stress and the role of ecological networks in enhancing carbon sinks. This section summarizes the research progress in several key areas, including heat and drought, ecological networks, and the impact of heat and drought on vegetation in desert ecosystems.

1.2.2 Ecological Networks: A Strategy for Restoration

Ecological networks (ENs) are strategically planned systems of interconnected natural and semi-natural areas designed to conserve biodiversity, enhance ecological processes and promote ecological sustainability.[31]. These networks incorporate ecological considerations into regional planning and ensure connectivity of natural habitats to enable species migration, gene flow, and resilience to environmental change.[32, 33]. The implementation of EN has demonstrated numerous benefits in various areas. In urban areas, EN promotes sustainable development by integrating green spaces to improve quality of life and support urban biodiversity. [34, 35], In desert ecosystems such as China, EN plays an important role in combating desertification by stabilizing soils, reducing erosion, and promoting the re-

establishment of native vegetation. [36, 37], Similarly, in the Argo-pastoral transition zone, the establishment of EN promotes the balance between agricultural productivity and ecological protection, thus achieving sustainable land use practices. [38, 39],

Although the benefits of EN are widely recognized, their implementation faces numerous challenges. Urbanization and infrastructure expansion often lead to habitat fragmentation, destroying the interconnectedness of natural landscapes and hindering ecological processes. Land-use conflicts arise when the interests of development and conservation conflict. Careful planning and engagement of stakeholders are needed to find balanced solutions. Environmental degradation due to pollution, overexploitation of resources and climate change further complicates the maintenance of functional and resilient EN. To address these challenges, a multi-pronged approach is needed. The focus here is on protecting natural resources, restoring degraded habitats and strengthening ecosystems. Strategies may include policy interventions, community engagement and the integration of ecological considerations into urban and regional planning. [33, 40, 41].

ENs development typically follows a structured framework with several key phases: Identification of ecological source areas: These are key habitats that provide a starting point for species dispersal and are essential for maintaining biodiversity and ecological integrity. Resistance surface optimization: This involves assessing and adjusting landscape elements to reduce barriers to species migration, thereby promoting connectivity between habitats. Ecological corridor extraction: Designing and constructing pathways that connect ecological source areas so that species can move and ecological processes can flow across the landscape. [42]. Identifying ecological source areas is a crucial first step because these areas are the starting points for species dispersal and are critical to the integrity of ecosystems. [43].

1.2.3 Enhancing Ecological Processes Through Spatial Optimization

Appropriate environmental conditions are essential to promote ecological processes; however, habitat fragmentation and the deterioration of natural resources hinder the ability of ecosystems to effectively maintain their functions. By optimizing spatial structure and establishing conservation measures, such as implementing stepping stones (small, strategic habitat patches that connect larger habitats), nutrient and energy cycling within the soil can be enhanced. This approach can improve soil quality and overall environmental health, ultimately creating favorable conditions for plant growth [44]. These initiatives significantly increase the ability of vegetation to act as a carbon sink, thereby contributing to carbon sequestration. [38].

Ecological corridors are essential for facilitating the movement and migration of species across fragmented landscapes. They serve as pathways connecting isolated habitats, promoting gene flow, species dispersal and biodiversity conservation.^[22, 45, 46] Despite the importance of ecological corridors, their implementation faces many challenges, including land use competition and insufficient regional cooperation. Addressing these barriers is essential to improving ecosystem resilience and genetic diversity, which plays a key role in ensuring ecological security.^[47] In addition, ecological corridors play an important role in limiting landscape fragmentation, improving species survival and optimizing ecosystem service functions^[27]. The Ecological Network (EN) has developed a network of organizations to further promote sustainable ecological management initiatives worldwide.^[48]

1.2.4 Research Objectives

This study aims to develop Ecological Spatial Networks (ESNs) to enhance carbon sequestration and achieve carbon neutrality in the Thal Desert, Punjab, Pakistan, which faces significant ecological and climate challenges. The main objective is to develop an innovative Ecological Spatial Network optimization method to identify key areas for ecological restoration using the Energy Flow and Connectivity Topology (EFCT) model. The specific objectives of this study are as follows:

- **Develop Ecological Spatial Networks (ESNs) to Enhance Carbon Sequestration:** Establish a spatial framework to enhance the carbon sequestration potential of desert ecosystems. To identify and optimize ecological patches, corridors, and stepping stones to increase landscape connectivity
- **Optimize ecological functions, connectivity, and topological properties:** To improve the efficiency of ecological restoration using the Energy Flow and Connectivity Topology (EFCT) model. To enhance the structural and functional properties of forests and wetlands to improve ecosystem resilience.
- **Identify key ecological nodes and corridors for restoration efforts:** To map and assess ecological resistance surfaces using the Minimum Cumulative Resistance (MCR) model. To identify ecological sources, hubs, and corridors that are critical for maintaining connectivity in desert landscapes.
- **Employ advanced geospatial and computational techniques:** Spatial analysis using ArcGIS to assess land cover, resistance surfaces, and ecological patterns. Implement Gephi for topological mapping to assess network stability and connectivity. Combine

Optimizing Ecological Spatial Networks for Carbon Sequestration and Climate Resilience: A Study of Ecological Restoration in the Thal Desert in Punjab, Pakistan

- energy flow models with complex network theory to assess the structural robustness of ecological spatial networks.
- Assess carbon sequestration potential and ecosystem resilience: Quantify the carbon storage capacity of different vegetation types within the Thal Desert. Assess the impact of ecological restoration strategies on improving carbon sequestration efficiency.
- Support climate change mitigation and sustainable development goals: Provide insights for effective climate adaptation and mitigation strategies for desert ecosystems. Provide recommendations for sustainable land management policies and ecological conservation in arid regions.

By achieving these goals, this study will help develop data-driven ecological restoration strategies that ensure improved ecosystem resilience, enhanced carbon storage potential, and a more sustainable landscape framework for the Thal Desert.

Chapter-II

2 Review of Literature

2.1 Landscape Spatial Structure and Carbon Neutrality

The structural aspects relating to the landscape spatial arrangement are critical in attaining carbon neutrality to avoid weather changes such as global warming. It is important to note that carbon neutrality is achieved by balancing carbon emissions and their corresponding sinks, thus enhancing the vegetation repairing process in disturbed regions such as arid, desert environments or habitats destroyed by human mining. Desertification and mining processes have significant and negative implications on the ecosystem in which there exists soil degradation alongside diminishing flora cover. Improvement of landscape connectivity or correlation of areas using models such as the EFCT model enhances the ecological functions of an area hence increasing the carbon sinks and increasing their resilience. Rather than simply linking ecological patches, the EFCT model enhances vegetation recovery, increasing carbon storage. It might be feasible to enhance the carbon estimation methods in future improvements to those such as LiDAR technology to create a more landscape restoration that will be effective for climate change^[37].

The way landscapes' spatial structures are significant in that they help support biodiversity and sustain ecological relationships between life forms. Understanding how spatial relationships work is made possible by applying complex network theory which assists in determining the critical 'nodes and links' that increase connectivity and strengthen ecological integrity. Such pursuits are aimed at building ecological networks that will reconnect fragmented areas to enhance biological diversity^[49]. The use of InVEST and MCR models has made it possible to evaluate different dimensions of ecological connectivity and formulate optimal spatial patterns. It has been established the role of edges which possess a high degree and links available for connections are fundamental in the conservation of biological diversity hence the reason for strategic action in ecologically critical areas. These spatial techniques assist in improving ecological processes, reducing habitat fragmentation, and contributing to ecological integrity in different parts of China^[50]. In this research paper context of critically impacted mining areas. The restoration of carbon sink function and the additional goals of carbon neutrality, the formation of an ecological network. The application of complex network theory in combination

with ecological indicators enables the quantitative determination of essential nodes and connections that serve the purpose of enhancing connectivity and carbon sequestration. Ecological network was constructed in Xuzhou, China by modifying Minimum cumulative resistance surface (MCR) to increase the plant cover development and landscape. The restoration of ecological networks is very important as they not only enhance the environmental resilience of the ecosystem which is crucial in attaining urban sustainability and climate goals. This research methodology provides an approach focused on the ecological rehabilitation of mines oil, increasing connectivity and ecological integrity which will help carbon neutrality^[41].

Changes in Land use cover (LULC) usually in areas such as the Yellow River Basin, the sustainable effect of carbon sequestration capacity enhances both natural and anthropogenic activities. Between 2000 to 2040, models such as Markova- PLUS and InVEST have been employed to predict land use change and assess carbon storage across various scenarios, demonstrating that carbon sequestration capacity is enhanced with reforestation and ecological restoration initiatives. The transformation of agricultural land into forested areas and urban green space into zones can significantly improve carbon sequestration, aiding in climate mitigation efforts. These techniques underscore the necessity for regulation that promotes ecological conservation and sustainable land usage, particularly in vulnerable regions such as the Yellow River Basin^[51]. Diminish initiatives for China on carbon fingerprint and fulfill its Paris Agreement commitment entail examining the factors contributing to carbon footprint pressure, contain population growth, economic development, technological progress, and vegetation quality. This paper applied the IPAT model and decoupling analysis to increase carbon emission, recent technology advancements have facilitated the decoupling of emissions from GDP growth, resulting in reductions in the carbon intensity science 2014. The quality of vegetation enhances carbon sequestration, understanding the critical role of forest protection in meaning carbon fingerprints. The finding suggests that China is progressing toward a balanced strategy of emission reduction that reconciles economic and environmental interests^[52].

Protecting and restoring forest ecosystems is crucial for enhancing carbon storage capacity and addressing climate change. This research focused on the ecological spatial network and examined the spatiotemporal changes in China's forest ecosystems between 2000 and 2018. This research employed complex network theory alongside the enhanced minimum cumulative resistance (MCR) model to demonstrate the significance of ecological nodes and corridors in carbon absorption. The research indicated that ecological restoration efforts enhanced the

quantity of ecological resources and corridors; however, the stability of the overall forest network diminished. Enhancing natural networks through the connection of fragmented areas and the reduction of redundant corridors can improve carbon absorption. This paper presents insights and strategies for advancing China's carbon neutrality and emission peak objectives via sustainable forest management^[38]In arid desert oasis environments, establishing an effective ecological network is essential for maintaining regional ecological security and fostering sustainable development. This study utilized the forest-grassland ecological network model, focusing on the desert oasis in Inner Mongolia, China, to simulate the connectivity between forests and grasslands by integrating ecological resistance and gravity. The findings indicate that rapid economic development can disrupt ecological networks, sever ecological corridors, and isolate critical ecological areas, consequently diminishing the connectivity and stability of the network. Well-designed development plans can enhance economic development and ecological integrity, serving as a model for sustainable planning in high-risk areas ^[53].

In arid regions like Dengkou County, China, optimizing ecological infrastructure is crucial for fostering sustainable urban development and addressing desertification. This research employed the minimum cumulative resistance (MCR) model to identify and prioritize ecological resources, nodes, and corridors aimed at enhancing the connectivity of urban ecological networks. The findings indicate that urbanization has led to a significant increase in landscape fragmentation within the region. This highlights the necessity of integrating ecological infrastructure into urban design to safeguard endangered ecosystems. This research develops a framework for coordinating urban development with environmental sustainability in ecologically sensitive areas ^[54]. Urban heat stress in densely populated areas is a major obstacle to sustainable development. This study investigated the effectiveness of stratified cooling systems in alleviating urban heat stress in the Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei (BTH) metropolitan area. The study used the minimum cumulative resistance (MCR) model to identify and classify ecological cooling points and corridors based on their cooling effects. The results showed that while some areas experienced cooling, cooling in extremely hot areas remained limited. Therefore, targeted development and improvement are needed. The study highlights the importance of incorporating natural cooling systems into urban planning to reduce heat-related stress and improve the liveability of growing metropolitan areas ^[55].

The notion of green ecological spatial networks encompasses landscape patterns, biological processes, and functions that enhance connectivity, safeguard biodiversity, and uphold ecosystem integrity. Research in this domain encompasses network creation, analysis, and

optimization, with applications in urban planning, hydrology, desertification mitigation, and soil conservation. Notable methodologies involve utilizing complex network theory to create resilient ecological networks that improve ecological stability and functional connectivity. The development of green ecological spatial networks seeks to address environmental issues through improved landscape connectivity and the integration of multidisciplinary approaches for sustainable management^[56]. The Kubuqi Desert in northern China has experienced notable ecological transformations as a result of both anthropogenic influences and natural factors. Studies carried out from 2000 to 2018 indicated that ecological protection measures, such as reforestation, soil restoration, and water resource management, play a crucial role in addressing desertification. The primary results indicate that grasslands are predominantly impacted by desertification, whereas urbanization and agricultural expansion have notably influenced land use patterns. The investigation emphasizes the necessity for fair ecological strategies to uphold ecosystem stability and reduce degradation risks, offering valuable perspectives for the sustainable management of desert ecosystems (2020-0242) ^[57].

This research assessed the ecological landscape risk and its causes in the Ordos-Yulin region utilizing land use data from 2000, 2010, and 2020. The primary findings indicated that grassland, cultivated land, and fallow land constituted the principal land use groups, whereas human actions, particularly ecological restoration efforts, significantly influenced landscape risk. The regions of elevated and moderate ecological risk initially increased and subsequently decreased. This demonstrates the stabilizing impact of ongoing environmental protection initiatives. The study showed that human disturbance, NDVI, and ecological policies were important factors affecting the ecological risk in the region. This underscores the necessity of harmonizing development and conservation to effectively oversee regional ecological stability^[58]. This study looked into soil heavy metal contamination utilizing hyperspectral technologies to indirectly identify heavy metal levels via vegetation analysis. Using peach trees from a contaminated location in northeastern Beijing, the researchers created prediction models to assess soil metal concentrations using leaf spectral reflectance data. The models correctly predicted levels of arsenic, lead, and cadmium, but had limited accuracy for other metals. The study emphasizes the potential of hyperspectral technology for extensive soil monitoring, as well as its advantages over standard chemical analysis approaches in determining environmental pollution^[59].

2.3 Spatial Structure and Biodiversity Conservation

This study aims to develop and improve the ecological network of wetlands in Dongying City, China, to reduce the ecological problems associated with urbanization. The study uses multiple models including MSPA, Conefor, and MCR to identify key ecological source locations and corridors, investigate network structure, and assess ecological risks. The results show that adding network edges significantly improves the robustness of ecological networks and promotes improvements in ecological connectivity and resilience to disturbances. This study highlights the importance of optimizing ecological networks for sustainable urban and regional design, especially in areas with fragile ecosystems^[60]. This study explored the optimization of ecological node configuration and the stability of ecological networks in arid areas, specifically Dengkou County, China. The study used the minimum cumulative resistance (MCR) model, supplemented by emerging theories, to identify ecological nodes and corridors that form a resilient network aimed at combating desertification. The arrangement of nodes was improved by using the Voronoi-based blind centroid scheme (BCBS) model, which significantly improved network stability and connectivity. The results showed that the optimized network exhibited a stronger ability to resist disturbance, providing important insights into the sustainable development and ecological resilience of fragile ecosystems (Yu et al., 2018)^[61].

This study analyzed landscape changes and optimized carbon sequestration strategies in mining areas of Xuzhou City from 2000 to 2020. It proposed an ecological spatial network using a synergistic model (SEEC) to combine biological functions with carbon sequestration capacity to enhance urban restoration. Spatial network analysis strengthens ecologically weak nodes by adding corridors and stepping stones, thereby improving ecological stability and connectivity. The study showed that the ecological network model is of great significance in restoring mining areas because it can enhance carbon sequestration and improve ecological resilience^[62]. This study assesses the spatiotemporal development of China's ecological spatial network, focusing on optimizing its function and structure and enhancing ecological resilience. The study used GIS and remote sensing data to analyze ecological services from 2005 to 2020, including water conservation, soil conservation, wind protection, etc. Using a complex network approach, the study showed that the strategic integration of ecological corridors and headwaters increased the robustness of the network and improved its resilience to random and targeted disturbances. This approach provides important insights into optimizing landscape connectivity for ecological sustainability^[63].

This study investigated the surface deformation characteristics of different vegetation types in the permafrost region of Linzhi, Tibet. Sentinel-1A data analyzed using PS-InSAR and SBAS-InSAR techniques helped monitor and predict the deformation of various vegetation types, including alpine vegetation, grassland, and coniferous forest. The study showed that surface deformation differed significantly with vegetation type and had a strong correlation with NDVI values. Surprisingly, grassland and alpine vegetation were generally associated with soil subsidence, while grassland and coniferous forest were associated with soil uplift. The Holt-Winters model was very effective in predicting future deformation. Therefore, this study is of great significance for ecological risk management and the promotion of sustainable practices in permafrost areas of Tibet. [64]. This study explored the correlation between the topological structure of forest and grassland eco-spatial networks in China and the supply of ecosystem services. This study used complex network theory and topological indicators such as PageRank, degree, and clustering coefficient to illustrate the role of these networks in promoting soil and water conservation and carbon storage. The results showed that ecosystem services are mainly located in southeastern China, where the connectivity of ecological resources is the strongest. The study emphasized that improving network connectivity, especially in damaged areas, can significantly improve ecosystem resilience and service supply [65].

2.4 Restoration of Carbon Sink Function in Mining Areas

This study explored the spatiotemporal dynamics of carbon use efficiency (CUE) in primary forests in southeastern Tibet, focusing on changes between different vegetation types and altitude zones. Analysis of MODIS data from 2000 to 2022 showed that carbon use efficiency (CUE) remained seasonally stable in high-altitude forests but showed significant fluctuations in grassland and desert areas. Regional climate factors, especially temperature, had a significant impact on CUE in different regions. Its sensitivity was greater in areas with less vegetation. This study highlights the importance of CUE analysis in assessing ecosystem carbon cycling and its sensitivity to environmental changes. It also emphasizes the need for local conservation strategies to enhance carbon sequestration [66].

This study evaluated the correlation between the structural characteristics of the forest-steppe ecological network and its ecological service capacity in the Wuding River Basin. The study analyzed ecological services such as sand fixation, soil conservation, and carbon sequestration from 2000 to 2020 and found that increased fragmentation affected the connectivity and overall ecological health of the network. This study used GIS spatial analysis and the minimum

cumulative resistance (MCR) model to delineate ecological corridors, revealing significant relationships between topological indicators such as clustering and ecosystem services. This integrated approach demonstrates the potential of network structure to improve ecological functions and provides valuable insights for sustainable landscape management in fragile environments ^[67]. This study introduces an innovative ecological spatial network model, For Eco-spatial Network, to optimize forest carbon storage in the Yellow River Basin. Using complex network theory, the researchers evaluated the spatial distribution of carbon density in 69 cities, with forest areas as nodes and ecological corridors as edges. The study used topological indicators (including clustering coefficient and betweenness) to enhance network resilience and optimize carbon sinks. The results showed that network optimization by improving ecological resources and corridors can significantly improve carbon storage and network stability, providing important inspiration for regional forest management and carbon neutrality initiatives ^[68].

This study investigated the effects of dust particle pollution on urban vegetation, focusing on *Euonymus japonicus*. The aim was to develop a model that can predict leaf dust deposition using hyperspectral data. The study analyzed dust deposition at three pollution levels. This showed that dust on leaves had a significant effect on spectral characteristics. The spectral reflectance curves showed significant changes before and after dust accumulation, especially in the range of 695~1400nm. This emphasizes that this band is particularly sensitive to dust detection. This study proposed a regression model using the leaf moisture index, which has a high prediction accuracy ($R^2=0.9019$). The model can effectively estimate the amount of dust deposited by urban vegetation and has certain guiding significance for urban air quality assessment and environmental management (Zhu et al., 2020)^[69]. This study used complex network theory and spatial data modeling to investigate the relationship between topological features of ecological networks and soil conservation capacity in southeastern Tibet. By analyzing indicators such as degree, clustering, and centrality in ecological spatial networks, the researchers established correlations between these topological features and soil conservation effects. The results showed that forest nodes with higher connectivity exhibited stronger soil conservation capacity, while grassland nodes with increased aggregation also contributed to enhanced conservation effects. This study proposed an integrated soil conservation and habitat quality assessment (ISHE) model, which aims at optimization to enhance ecosystem resilience and provide practical suggestions for ecological restoration programs ^[70]

2.5 Land Use Changes and Carbon Sequestration

A comprehensive assessment of the ecological sensitivity and landscape pattern of abandoned mining sites was conducted, highlighting the need to integrate ecological sensitivity with landscape planning to promote sustainable development. The study established a land use planning framework by analyzing factors such as topography, water systems, and vegetation landscapes, addressing specific environmental challenges associated with mining site degradation. This study emphasizes the need to balance ecological protection and economic development by proposing zoning strategies to improve restoration outcomes while supporting recreational and economic activities consistent with environmental resilience. This study used a GIS-based analysis and sensitivity mapping approach and provided a systematic framework to assess landscapes affected by industrial activities and inform ecological restoration initiatives aimed at achieving long-term sustainability ^[71]. The development of a water-based ecological network in Danko County, characterized by arid and semi-arid conditions, was investigated. The authors analyzed groundwater and surface water distribution, using empirical mode decomposition (EMD) and point pattern analysis to develop a network designed to enhance ecological stability. This approach highlights the importance of water sources such as artificial oases in combating desertification and promoting sustainable development while using ecological corridors to connect fragmented landscapes. This study highlights the importance of water resource management in ecologically sensitive areas and provides a useful framework for similar situations ^[54]. This study aims to mitigate the hot urban climate through a cascade cooling system designed for the Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei (BTH) urban agglomeration. This study examined urban heat stress and quantified ecological patches and cooling corridors to evaluate their cooling effects. This showed that the urban agglomeration exhibited a spatial hierarchy in terms of cooling functions. The authors used the minimum cumulative resistance (MCR) model to describe the hierarchical system of cooling spots and corridors and classified them according to their effectiveness in mitigating the urban heat island effect. The results showed that ecological regions such as forests and wetlands made important contributions to urban heat management. However, the connectivity and quality of these areas remain problematic. This paper highlights the importance of ecological land connectivity in urban planning to cope with urban heat impacts. Practical recommendations for sustainable urban development are also provided^[71].

This study used the Biome-BGC model to simulate net biome productivity (NBP) and investigated the correlation between the topological characteristics of the vegetation ecospatial

network and its carbon sequestration potential in the Yellow River Basin of China. The results showed a negative linear correlation between the betweenness centrality of forest nodes and their carbon sequestration. In contrast, grassland nodes showed a positive correlation with the clustering coefficient, indicating that topological characteristics significantly affect the carbon capture potential of vegetation. This study proposed optimization strategies, including the establishment of ecological corridors to enhance carbon sequestration in forest and grassland nodes, to match China's carbon neutrality goals^[72]. A comprehensive analysis was conducted on the impact of the structural characteristics of China's forest and grassland ecological spatial networks on ecosystem service functions such as water and soil conservation, soil conservation, and carbon storage. The study showed that the ecological network in southeastern China showed stronger connectivity and supported higher levels of ecosystem services than the more fragmented landscapes in the northwest. The study found that basic topological indicators including PageRank, betweenness, and clustering coefficient play a vital role in identifying areas where network optimization can improve ecological stability and service provision. This study highlights the importance of spatial planning and ecological network optimization for improving environmental resilience and ecosystem health^[65].

The correlation between the structural characteristics of ecological spatial networks and their carbon sequestration capacity was studied, focusing on ecologically vulnerable areas in Inner Mongolia. The study identified key ecological nodes and corridors for enhancing net primary productivity (NPP) by analyzing topological indicators (including connectivity and resilience) within grasslands and agro-pastoral transition zones. The results showed that grasslands contributed significantly to network stability and carbon sequestration, while areas with sparse connectivity (such as certain forests) had less impact on ecosystem resilience. The study highlights the importance of improving connectivity by incorporating ecological corridors to enhance carbon sequestration and promote regional carbon neutrality goals. This study emphasizes the need for targeted restoration efforts in areas with high carbon emissions and the importance of strategically placing nodes and corridors to improve ecological outcomes (Wang et al., 2022).^[64]

2.6 Carbon Fingerprint and Reduction Strategies

The correlation between the topological characteristics of the ecological spatial network and soil conservation function in southeastern Tibet was studied. The authors used complex network theory to study the connectivity, robustness, and soil conservation potential of the

ecological network based on remote sensing data. The results showed that topological indicators such as degree and centrality were positively correlated with the soil conservation capacity of forest nodes. The authors proposed strategies to improve ecological resilience using the integrated soil conservation and habitat quality evaluation (ISHE) model. The focus was on optimizing the robustness of the network through targeted interventions such as ecological stepping stones and corridors. This approach provides a framework for protecting ecologically fragile areas by improving soil conservation and ecosystem stability [70]. To study the decoupling of China's carbon footprint (CFP) from GDP and identify the factors influencing CFP. This study uses the IPAT equation and the Log Mean Divisia Index (LMDI) to analyze the factors influencing the carbon footprint (CFP), focusing on the temporal and spatial changes from 2000 to 2017. Economic growth has significantly driven the increase in CFP, while technological progress has played a role in reducing it. Population dynamics and improvements in vegetation quality are influencing factors, as population growth generally leads to an increase in CFP, while a decrease in vegetation quality tends to reduce CFP. The study highlights that China's economic growth and carbon emissions are shifting to a "weak to strong" decoupling phase, suggesting a favorable outcome for achieving the Paris Agreement goals [52]

In this study, we found that land use and land cover change (LULCC) and climate change affect emissions in the upper Yangtze River. The authors used the SWAT model combined with statistical techniques to assess the impact of these changes on emission patterns. The results showed that climate change played a dominant role, causing 98% of the increase in runoff, while land use and land cover change (LULCC) accounted for only 2%. This study shows that it is important to distinguish between natural and human impacts on water resources. This is crucial for sustainable watershed management in ecologically sensitive areas [73]. A detailed overview of ecosystem services (ESS) valuation methodologies and advances, focusing on spatial mapping, is offered. For better land use policy, green accounting, resource allocation, and ecosystem service payments, spatially explicit valuing of ecosystem services is needed. Schägner et al. emphasize that ecosystem services (ESS) assessment methods range from simple land use/cover (LULC) proxies to complicated models that include value functions and raw data validation. The research indicates a shift towards complicated, regionally heterogeneous assessments of environmental services across areas to improve policy coordination. The authors note that spatial ESS maps have many benefits, but precision, accuracy, and policy recommendations are still difficult. Data availability and methodological

rigor differ. Developing ecosystem service models, increasing value transfer functions, and studying biodiversity and ecological resilience are important research areas [74].

Integrate ecosystem characteristics and ultimate ecosystem services to enhance sustainable public policy decisions. The authors highlight the “data gap” that impedes accurate assessment and valuation of ecosystem services and propose a 10-step framework to address this gap by integrating data and methods from the ecological, economic, and policy domains. The approach includes estimating ecosystem characteristics through biophysical models, determining ultimate ecosystem services through measurable endpoints, and quantifying trade-offs using ecological production functions to assist decision-makers in assessing and managing ecosystem services. The framework is important for guiding policy decisions that need to strike a balance between ecological sustainability and societal benefits [75]. Numerous studies have been conducted to explore the relationship between climate change and forest ecosystems. In addition, the impacts of changes in temperature and precipitation patterns on ecosystem services have been demonstrated (Matthews et al., 2013). This study assessed the sensitivity of various forest types in the eastern United States, specifically within military installations, to predict the impacts of climate-induced habitat changes on essential ecosystem services, including carbon storage and water regulation. The study analyzed 134 tree species using species distribution models and developed the Forest-Related Climate Vulnerability Index (FRICV) to assess the risk to ecosystem functions at specific locations under different climate scenarios. The study showed that changes in existing tree species due to climate stresses have an impact on forest composition and the provision of ecosystem services. This highlights the need for adaptive management strategies to address these impacts.[76]. In the ecosystem services literature, emphasis has been placed on the complex relationships between ecosystem characteristics and the services they provide. These services play a vital role in human well-being and determine environmental policy. The ecosystem services framework outlined by Apitz (2012) includes both direct and indirect contributions of ecosystems, linking ecological processes to economic and policy considerations. The framework provides reliable metrics for quantifying ecosystem services, which is essential for informed policy decisions that take into account ecological, economic and social trade-offs. Methods for mapping ecosystem service values have improved, with contemporary studies using spatially explicit methods and value transfer techniques, as noted by Costanza et al. (1997) and later studies. These methods show considerable variation, highlighting the importance of advanced GIS technology and spatial modelling in capturing differences in ecosystem services across landscapes. Wong et al. (2014)

stressed the need for reliable measurement methods to link ecological attributes to ultimate ecosystem services and promote more consistent strategies in policy frameworks to achieve sustainable development goals through ecosystem services assessment [77].

The Chinese Ecosystem Research Network (CERN) embodies China's commitment to ecological research and sustained ecosystem monitoring. Founded in 1988, CERN coordinates monitoring, research, and demonstration through an extensive network of 40 field stations, 5 sub-centers, and 1 integrated center. These represent a variety of ecosystem types across China, such as croplands, forests, grasslands, deserts, and aquatic systems (Fu et al., 2010). The network's main goals are to monitor long-term changes, conduct multi-site studies, and promote data sharing for ecological research at national and international levels. Thanks to CERN's efforts, research on carbon cycling, ecosystem structure, biodiversity, and the impacts of human activities on ecosystems has made significant progress. The research program focuses on the management and restoration of ecosystems affected by urbanization and other anthropogenic pressures. CERN is an important research platform that influences China's approaches to environmental protection, resource management, and ecosystem restoration. Future strategic goals for CERN include expanding monitoring programs, strengthening data integration, and improving ecosystem management practices to address China's changing ecological challenges [78]. The article "The Impact of Climate Change and Human Activities on NDVI of Vegetation in Maowusu Desert, China from 2000 to 2019" analyzes in detail the changes in vegetation cover in Maowusu Desert caused by climate and human activities. This study used the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) data from 2000 to 2019 to evaluate the spatiotemporal distribution of vegetation cover in this ecologically sensitive area. The results showed that vegetation in the eastern and southeastern regions improved significantly, while there was little change in the central and northwestern regions. The results showed that human activities contributed 62.68% to vegetation improvement, and climate factors contributed 37.32%. This study shows that ecosystem restoration initiatives, including reforestation, are very effective in addressing desertification. This study can also provide a reference for ecological management strategies in similar regions [79].

The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) was used as a metric to study the impact of climate change and human activities on vegetation cover in the Maowusu Sandy Land from 2000 to 2019. The study found that human activities, especially reforestation and land management practices, played an important role in improving vegetation in the region. They accounted for 62.68% of the recorded increase in NDVI. In contrast, climate factors explained

37.32% of vegetation changes. Spatial analysis showed that vegetation improved significantly in the eastern and southeastern regions, while changes were small in the central and northwestern regions. This study highlights the importance of human-led restoration initiatives in improving the resilience of ecosystems in semi-arid regions to desertification ^[79]. This paper investigates the impact of tropical Pacific changes on global mean surface temperature (GMST) and global warming trends as described in the study by Wang et al. (2017). The Tropical Pacific Index (TPI) was developed using a multi-model ensemble approach to monitor changes in sea surface temperature (SST). The results show that the mean surface temperature (GMST) and TPI are strongly correlated on the interannual time scale, while a more complex relationship is observed on the decadal scale. This dependence suggests that the traditional GMST regression equation may underestimate the response of the decadal changes in the tropical Pacific. The study shows that model-based simulations exhibit significant variations, especially in high latitudes, which means that the response of GMST to tropical Pacific changes is sensitive to the model used and is affected by internal and external factors, including volcanic activity and anthropogenic aerosols. The results emphasize the need for improved observational constraints and further refinement of models to understand the impact of the Pacific on decadal climate change, especially those associated with global warming events ^[80].

The Remote Sensing Ecological Index (RSEI), which integrates greenness, humidity, drought, and heat, was introduced to map the spatiotemporal changes in ecological conditions in Fujian Province, China from 2002 to 2017. This study used MODIS data, the Mann-Kendall test, and change vector analysis (CVA) to assess trends. The results showed that forest coverage and ecological quality increased significantly. At the same time, ecological quality in coastal areas declined due to urbanization. The spatial resolution of the RSEI was improved by applying clearer surface temperature images, making it an efficient tool for monitoring changes over time. The method showed that the RSEI can conduct comprehensive ecological monitoring and, unlike traditional methods, it provides a spatially detailed comprehensive image rather than a single numerical value ^[81]. The impact of land use change on the net primary productivity (NPP) of the Beijing urban agglomeration was studied, highlighting the importance of sustainable land management in the context of rapid urbanization. This study used the Patch Generation Land Use Simulation (PLUS) model combined with various statistical analyses to investigate the spatiotemporal development of NPP from 2000 to 2020. It also projected future NPP trends under different scenarios, including baseline, farmland protection, and ecological protection. The results showed that urban expansion had a significant impact on NPP. Higher NPP levels

were observed in densely forested mountainous areas. This study highlights the importance of wise ecological management to achieve stable or improved NPP trends, thereby promoting the coexistence of urban development and ecological sustainability ^[82]. Recent research suggests that spatial analysis platforms such as Google Earth Engine (GEE) and models such as the Integrated Valuation and Trade-offs of Ecosystem Services (InVEST) should be integrated. This study investigated the impact of forest cover loss on carbon sequestration, particularly in the hilly regions of Bangladesh, where deforestation has led to a decline in carbon storage capacity^[83].

2.7 Forest Ecosystem Restoration and Carbon Storages

The dynamic land system (DLS) model and the integrated valuation and trade-offs of environmental services (InVEST) model were used to study the impact of land use change on carbon storage in Pakistan. Three scenarios were simulated: business as usual (BAU), investment priority orientation (IPO) and ecological conservation orientation (ECO), and the carbon storage forecast for 2020 was evaluated based on the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC). The results showed that carbon storage decreased under the BAU scenario, while it increased under the IPO and ECO scenarios. In addition, the carbon storage potential was the highest under the ECO scenario. However, considering the socio-economic needs of Pakistan, the role of ECO is limited, and IPO is a more realistic option to achieve sustainable development and protect carbon stocks in the region^[84]. Carbon stocks in mountain forests of the Bagrot Valley in the Karakoram range have been extensively studied. The InVEST model uses Sentinel-2 satellite data to classify land use and estimate carbon stocks in different forest types. The results show that dense coniferous forests are the most important carbon sink in the region, with an estimated economic value of \$74,728 per hectare. The results suggest that spatially explicit tools such as InVEST play an important role in improving the management of carbon stocks in mountain ecosystems, which is critical for climate regulation and REDD+ initiatives ^[85].

Recent studies have revealed the intricate links between ecosystem services and land-use change, with a focus on carbon sequestration. According to a study by Fadaei et al. (2020), carbon sequestration in Iran's Jahannama Reserve was significantly affected by land cover changes in forests and grasslands. The study used InVEST software to estimate the reduction in carbon stocks due to expected land cover changes, an important tool for future land-use planning. Mapped carbon stocks in forest areas of Pakistan. This illustrates the geographic

distribution of carbon stocks and highlights key conditions for sustainable management to limit carbon losses. To support regional conservation efforts, the study focused on identifying locations with high carbon density using geospatial methods. Additionally, We developed a remote sensing ecological index (RSEI) that takes into account multiple environmental factors such as greenness and humidity to assess ecological degradation in Fujian Province, China. This study shows that remote sensing can provide effective assistance for monitoring long-term ecological changes, especially in urban environments. This will improve the possibilities of ecological monitoring and management ^[81].

The impacts of land use and land cover (LULC) changes on ecosystem services in the subtropical shrubland of Soan Valley, Pakistan were investigated with a focus on carbon sequestration dynamics. The study used Landsat imagery from 2007, 2013, and 2019 to predict future land use and land cover (LULC) using a CA-Markov model. It incorporated spatial land use and land cover data into the InVEST carbon model to examine changes in carbon stocks. The results showed an increase in tree cover, especially species such as *Acacia* and *Olea*, which enhanced the prediction of carbon sequestration to 2030. The findings highlight the importance of protecting forest cover for carbon sequestration, as changes in land use and land cover affect ecosystem services, which can be enhanced or weakened depending on management strategies ^[86]. Recent studies have shown that translating habitat quality into ecological risk is important for effectively managing ecosystems affected by development. Zhang et al. (2022) used the InVEST model to assess habitat quality in the Suzhou section of the Grand Canal and found that large-scale expansion increased the area of robust habitats such as wetlands and forests, making downstream areas vulnerable to pollution and spills. Environmental Navigation. Their study demonstrates the importance of habitat quality modeling in determining deterministic ecological protection. It is a treatment support tool that can be tailored for different regions ^[87].

The article "A Conceptual Approach to Model the Geospatial Impacts of Typical Urban Threats on River Corridor Habitat Quality" uses the InVEST (Integrated Assessment of Habitat Quality in River Corridors - Environmental Services and Trade-offs) habitat quality model to study the impacts of urbanization on river corridor habitat quality. The study analyzed urban hazards such as development areas, transportation systems, and water pollution in the Pochote River in León, Nicaragua, to assess their individual and cumulative effects on habitat quality. The results showed that habitat quality was severely degraded, especially in adjacent metropolitan areas, and that multiple stressors worked together to affect biodiversity conservation. The study shows that the InVEST model accurately depicts the spatial impacts of urbanization on river

ecosystems and is an important tool for urban planning and ecological protection of urban river environments ^[88]. An integrated model for forest fire risk prediction in China was developed by combining random forest (RF), support vector machine (SVM), gradient-boosted decision tree (GBDT), and logistic regression (LR) classifiers. The model achieved high prediction accuracy with an AUC of 0.97 based on satellite data and geospatial analysis, especially highlighting high-risk areas in the northeast and southwest. This study showed that ensemble learning is effective for mapping environmental risks. The potential of the model to support proactive forest management and fire suppression strategies was also highlighted (Shao et al., 2023) ^[89]. The remote sensing ecological index (RSEI) based on MODIS data was used to analyze the ecological quality of urban areas on the northern slope of the Tianshan Mountains, and the changes in ecological space and quality from 2000 to 2020 were evaluated. The analysis showed that although the ecological quality has recently begun to decline, it has improved overall, and the RSEI in the "significantly improved" (IO) area indicates that vegetation development is the main influencing factor, while high temperature and drought harm ecological quality. The authors emphasize that in the rapid urbanization process in the arid areas of the Tianshan Mountains, urban development that maintains ecological sovereignty is crucial ^[90].

2.8 Ecological Network in Arid and Semi-Arid Environments

The relationship between eco-spatial network structure and carbon use efficiency (CUE) in the Wuding River Basin was investigated. This study highlights the importance of eco-spatial networks, which consist of nodes representing biologically important sites and corridors as connecting edges, in elucidating ecosystem processes. The study used MODIS satellite data to measure carbon use efficiency (CUE), which is the ratio of net primary productivity (NPP) to gross primary productivity (GPP). This helps to assess the carbon sequestration efficiency of different landscapes. The results showed a strong positive correlation between CUE and network metrics, including closeness centrality and betweenness centrality. This suggests that nodes with high connectivity and importance in ecological networks can improve carbon use efficiency. This study highlights the importance of network analysis in assessing ecological health and developing conservation strategies, as it can identify areas with strong connectivity and high carbon sequestration potential ^[91]. In Linfen, China, they studied the dynamics of ecological networks in mining areas, combining ecological restoration programs with complex network optimization. The study examined land use changes between 2005 and 2020 and assessed the ecological risks of the landscape. Particular attention was paid to the impacts of

urban expansion and coal mining on ecological stability. They constructed ecological networks with optimized resilience and connectivity using the minimum cumulative resistance (MCR) model, taking into account aspects such as the self-repair capacity of ecosystems and the connectivity of ecological patches. Their results showed that local ecological hazards in Linfen decreased as the restoration program progressed. However, high-risk areas still exist near cities and mining areas. This paper advocates the implementation of ecological networks to improve connectivity and resilience in mining landscapes, coordinate conservation with socioeconomic needs, and achieve more sustainable urban planning and land management ^[92] .

An analysis of carbon emissions from Pakistan's energy sector shows that there is an urgent need to shift away from fossil fuels to more sustainable energy options. Pakistan is suffering from severe impacts of climate change and is highly vulnerable to environmental and public health threats. The energy sector is heavily dependent on natural gas, oil, and coal and is the main source of carbon emissions in the country. Changes in energy sources in recent years have made us more dependent on coal, especially for power generation. This leads to higher CO₂ emissions as coal has a higher CO₂ intensity compared to alternative fuels. Natural gas remains the main energy source, but oil use in the transportation sector and coal use in the cement sector contribute significantly to emissions. Research shows that shifting to renewable energy sources such as solar and wind can reduce environmental and economic burdens. However, policy and planning shortcomings have hindered this progress ^[93]. The ecological spatial network of the Yellow River Basin (YRB) in China and its correlation with vegetation carbon use efficiency (CUE), a key indicator for understanding the relationship between climate change and carbon cycle, was analyzed. Using remote sensing data, CASA and LUE-NDWI models were used to calculate carbon use efficiency (CUE), and the results showed that CUE of various vegetation types decreased from west to east. The minimum cumulative resistance (MCR) model was used to identify natural resources and corridors, and the results showed that the connectivity in the upstream area was improved, and there was a significant correlation between network topology indicators and CUE. This study recommends optimization strategies, such as strengthening ecological corridors and formulating protection measures, to improve carbon cycle efficiency and promote ecological sustainability in the Yellow River Basin ^[94] .

This study investigated the effects of drought and water use efficiency (WUE) on greening patterns in the Yellow River Basin. The Yellow River Basin is an important natural region in China. A large-scale reforestation program is currently underway. Leaf area index (LAI) was used to measure greenness. In addition, Geo Detector, random forest regression, and structural

equation models were used to assess the effects of environmental variables such as temperature and precipitation on greening patterns in different basins. The results showed that the greening levels in the upper, middle, and lower reaches were significant. Among them, the most important influencing factors were: water use efficiency (WUE) and annual minimum temperature played a dominant role in the upper reaches, and extreme drought and WUE in the middle reaches had a significant impact. The authors emphasized the importance of interactions between factors and pointed out that the combined effects of drought and water scarcity are often greater than the effects of a single cause. This study highlights the need to develop adaptive, evidence-based reforestation technologies that take into account the different ecological environments in arid and semi-arid regions ^[95]. This study examined the impact of climate on the efficiency of carbon use in terrestrial ecosystems around the world. This efficiency is expressed as the ratio of net primary productivity (NPP) to gross primary productivity (GPP). Analysis of MODIS data from the last decade showed a decreasing trend in the NPP/GPP ratio between 2000 and 2009. This was mainly due to rising temperatures, stable GPP, and declining NPP. Rising temperatures led to a decrease in the NPP/GPP ratio, but increased precipitation appears to increase it. The results highlight the complex interactions between climate variables and the distribution of carbon in ecosystems. They emphasize that climate change is reducing the efficiency of global carbon storage, especially in warmer and drier regions ^[96].

This study focused on optimizing ecological spatial networks (ESNs) to enhance carbon sequestration and achieve carbon neutrality in the Thal Desert of Punjab, Pakistan. The study used the minimum cumulative resistance (MCR) model to identify key ecological patches and corridors for enhanced connectivity and resilience. Topological network analysis was used to assess network robustness, and the ecological corridors were refined using the ecological function, connectivity, and topology (EFCT) model. The results showed that 27 new ecological sites and 51 ecological corridors were added, and the connectivity and carbon sequestration capacity were significantly improved by 14.97%. The results showed that the northeast and southwest regions had strong ecological functionality but poor connectivity, while the central region had strong connectivity but low ecological benefits. Optimizing ecological networks can improve resilience and enhance carbon sequestration. The study concluded that this provides a practical solution for sustainable land management and climate change mitigation in arid areas ^[97].

Chapter-III

3 Overview of study area and research content

3.1 Overview of the Study Area

3.1.1 Geographical Location

The Thal Desert is situated in the central region of Punjab, Pakistan, between latitudes 31°10' N and longitudes 71°30' E. It spans approximately 190 miles (310 kilometers) in length and up to 70 miles (113 kilometers) in width. This arid expanse is bounded by the Salt Range to the north, the Indus River floodplains to the west, and the Jhelum and Chenab River floodplains to the east. Administratively, it encompasses parts of the Bhakkar, Khushab, Mianwali, Jhang, Layyah, and Muzaffargarh districts. As shown in Figure 2.1

Figure 3.1 | Overview of the study area.

3.1.2. Topographic and Geomorphic Features

The topography of the Thal Desert is characterized by a series of sand ridges and undulating sandy plains interspersed with flat, narrow valleys more suitable for agriculture. The altitude is about 200 meters in the north, gradually decreasing to about 120 meters in the south. The main landscape here is dunes, some of which are as high as 175 meters. They cover about 50-60% of the desert area. These dunes are mainly composed of wind-eroded sediments deposited by the Indus River.

3.1.3. Climate and Hydrological Characteristics

The Thal Desert has a harsh subtropical climate with wide temperature fluctuations. Summers are extremely hot, with average temperatures of around 35°C in June and July, often soaring to over 45°C due to hot southerly winds. Winters are cold, with temperatures ranging between 3°C and 8°C, occasionally approaching freezing in January. Annual rainfall is scanty and erratic, averaging between 150 and 350 mm, and occurs mainly during the monsoon season from June to August. The region is also affected by strong winds throughout the year, causing wind erosion and dust storms, posing challenges for agriculture and settlement.

3.1.4. Vegetation Distribution Characteristics

Despite its arid environment, the Thal Desert is home to a variety of drought-tolerant vegetation. The vegetation here is mainly composed of short, thorny shrubs, among which species such as Acacia dominate. Perennial herbaceous plants are also common because they are adapted to very low and irregular rainfall. These plant species are essential for stabilizing the soil and providing fodder for local livestock. However, overgrazing and human activities have led to the degradation of vegetation, exacerbating soil erosion and desertification processes.

3.1.5 Socioeconomic characteristics

The Thal Desert stretches across several districts in Pakistan's Punjab province, where residents rely primarily on agriculture and animal husbandry for their livelihoods. Despite the dry environment, these activities form the backbone of the region's economy. Agriculture in the Thal Desert is highly dependent on rainfall, which is scarce and irregular. Farmers grow drought-tolerant crops, with chickpeas being an important cash crop. The success of chickpea farming is closely tied to rainfall intensity and distribution, making it an important source of income for rural communities. Efforts to implement improved agricultural techniques have the potential to increase farm yields despite inherent climatic challenges. Animal husbandry plays

an important role in the socioeconomic fabric of the Thal Desert. The region is home to many native livestock species, including camels, sheep, goats, cattle, and buffalo. Camel farming is an important part of the livelihoods of many residents, providing milk, meat, and transportation. However, camel production faces many constraints, such as limited veterinary services, feed shortages due to climate change, and inadequate market infrastructure. Addressing these challenges is critical to improving the socioeconomic status of camel herders and ensuring sustainable livestock production.

The Thal Desert region faces several economic challenges, including poverty and limited infrastructure. The number of people living in poverty is affected by income volatility. Livestock is an important means of alleviating poverty. In addition to being a source of income, livestock can also serve as a buffer against crop failures, thereby increasing the resilience of rural households. Despite its importance, livestock production is hampered by factors such as inadequate veterinary care, scarce feed, and limited access to markets. All of these hinder the potential to improve the socioeconomic status of the rural population. The Thal Desert is home to several tribes, including the Tiwana, Siar, Mamak, Bachal, Baghel, Ladari, and Jamat. The main language is Siraki, but Punjabi is also widely spoken in some areas. The population lives in small, scattered settlements, often lacking basic amenities such as electricity, clean water, and sanitation. Healthcare is limited, and many villages lack indoor toilets and medical facilities. This has led to a wide range of health issues, including chronic gastrointestinal problems and maternal health issues. Recognizing the socioeconomic challenges, several development initiatives have been proposed to improve the living conditions of the people of the Thal Desert. Projects focused on increasing agricultural productivity, improving livestock management practices, and developing infrastructure are crucial. For example, the proposed second phase of the Great Thal Canal aims to irrigate large areas of land, which has the potential to transform the agricultural landscape and boost local production, thereby promoting economic development in the region.

In summary, the socioeconomic identity of the Thal Desert is shaped by its reliance on agriculture and animal husbandry under challenging environmental conditions. Addressing the region's economic and infrastructure constraints through targeted development initiatives is essential to improving the quality of life of the region's residents.

3.2 Data Source and Processing

This study combines multiple datasets to analyze the ecological status, land cover changes, and environmental characteristics of the Thal Desert in Punjab, Pakistan. The data sources include satellite remote sensing products, socioeconomic statistics, topographic information, vegetation indices, accessibility data, and meteorological data. Table 1 summarizes the data used and their resolution, time range, and sources. In addition, the spatial representation of the dataset is visualized in Figure 2.

Figure 3.2 1 The datasets are derived from multiple sources of remote sensing and geospatial information

3.2.1 Data Sources

The datasets used include various environmental and socio-economic parameters related to the Thal Desert region of Punjab Province, Pakistan. Table 1 provides an overview of these datasets including their type, spatial resolution, temporal coverage, and sources.

Table 3.2.1 1 Data source in the Thal Desert area in Punjab, Pakistan.

Data	Type	Resolution	Year	Sources
Land Cover Type Global	Yearly	Raster 500m	2000 - 2022	https://lpdaac.usgs.gov/products/mcd12q1v006/
DEM		Raster 30m	2021	https://code.earthengine.google.com/
NDVI		Raster 250m	2021	https://code.earthengine.google.com/
MNDWI		Raster 250m	2021	https://code.earthengine.google.com/
VFC		Raster 250m	2021	https://code.earthengine.google.com/
Water network density		Vector -	2021	http://www.OpenStreetMap.org/
Road network density		Vector -	2021	http://www.OpenStreetMap.org/
Mean annual temperature		Raster 1000m	2000 - 2022	https://code.earthengine.google.com/
Slope		Raster 30m	2021	https://code.earthengine.google.com/
Population Density		Raster 1000m	2000 - 2022	http://www.worldpop.org/
Nighttime Light		Raster 463.83 m	200- 2022	https://code.earthengine.google.com/
Administrative divisions		Vector -	2021	https://diva-gis.org/data.html

Detailed Description of Datasets in Table 1

Land Cover Type Data: Source: The Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) MCD12Q1.061 product provides global 500-meter resolution annual land cover data from 2000 to 2022. This dataset uses a supervised classification algorithm to classify land cover into different categories, including forest land, cropland, water bodies, wetlands, shrubs, grasslands, bare land, and artificial surfaces. The data can be accessed through the Land Processes Distributed Active Archive Center (LP DAAC).

Socio-Economic Data: Population density: This dataset comes from WorldPop and provides high-resolution gridded population estimates, making it easy to analyze changes in population distribution and density over time.

Night light data: This data comes from the Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite (VIIRS) on Google Earth Engine, which captures the intensity of artificial lighting at night, providing insights into human activities and urbanization patterns.

Terrain Data: Digital Elevation Model (DEM): The Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) DEM has a spatial resolution of 30 meters and provides detailed information about the height of the Earth's surface, which is essential for topographic and hydrological analysis.

Slope Data: Slope data comes from DEMs and represents the steepness or slope of the terrain, which is essential for understanding erosion patterns, land stability, and suitability for different land uses.

Vegetation Data: Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI): This index measures the health and density of vegetation by analyzing the difference between near-infrared and red-light reflectance. Higher NDVI values generally indicate healthier and denser vegetation.

Modified Normalized Difference Water Index (MNDWI): The MNDWI is used to improve views of open water while suppressing noise from built-up areas, vegetation, and soil. This index is valuable for water management and wetland studies.

Vegetation Cover (VFC): This metric quantifies the percentage of land area covered by vegetation and helps assess land degradation, desertification, and ecological health.

Accessibility Data: Density of road and water networks: These vector datasets come from OpenStreetMap and provide information on the distribution and density of transport and hydrological networks. This is essential for accessibility analyses, infrastructure planning, and understanding the interaction between people and their environment.

Meteorological Data: Temperature and precipitation: Climate data, including mean annual temperature and precipitation, from Google Earth Engine. These datasets are critical for analyzing climate trends, assessing their impacts on ecosystems, and developing environmental management strategies.

3.2.1.1 Data Preprocessing

Several preprocessing steps were performed to ensure data consistency and accuracy: Data cleaning Datasets were checked for missing values, duplications, and inconsistencies. Vector data (roads and water networks) were thinned to remove errors such as gaps and overlaps. Spatial resampling All raster datasets were resampled to a uniform resolution of 200 m to ensure consistency in analysis. Projection alignment was performed to maintain a common coordinate reference system. Data normalization NDVI, MNDWI, and VFC values were normalized to a range of 0 to 1 for comparison. Night light intensity was scaled to remove outliers. Raster processing Slope maps were generated from the DEM using ArcGIS surface analysis tools. Distance grids for roads and water networks were created using Euclidean distance analysis. Software and tools used The following geospatial tools and programming platforms were used: Google Earth Engine (GEE): for remote sensing image processing and vegetation index calculation. ArcGIS 10.4.8: for spatial analysis, resampling, and cartographic visualization. Python: for automation, data extraction, and statistical analysis. Gephi 0.10.0: for topological mapping and connectivity assessment. MATLAB R2023b: for advanced modeling and numerical analysis. Origin 2021: for data visualization. EndNote 21: for managing references and citations.

3.2.1.2 Data Visualization and Representation

The spatial distribution of the key datasets used in this study is shown in Figure 2, including: (a) Land cover type: which shows the classification of different land types. (b) MNDWI: highlights water bodies and humidity levels. (c) VFC: shows the vegetation cover fraction of the study area. (d) NDVI: indicates vegetation health and density. (e) Road network density: illustrates accessibility and transportation network. (f) Water network density: describes the distribution of water bodies. (g) Temperature distribution: highlights thermal variations in the area. (h) Slope data: indicates terrain elevation and steepness. (i) Night light data: captures human settlement and urbanization patterns. These datasets provide a comprehensive understanding of the ecological and environmental dynamics of the Thal Desert, supporting subsequent analysis of ecological network development and optimization.

This section details the various datasets used in the study, their sources, and the pre-processing methods used to ensure data integrity and usability. By integrating land cover, socioeconomic, topographic, vegetation, accessibility, and meteorological data, this study lays a solid foundation for spatial and ecological analysis. The integration of remote sensing, GIS, and

statistical modeling techniques ensures a high-resolution, multi-temporal assessment of the ecological status of the Thal Desert.

3.2.3 Research Content

This study aims to develop an Ecological Spatial Network (ESN) for the Thal Desert, Punjab, Pakistan, focusing on enhancing carbon sequestration, ecological connectivity, and environmental resilience. The research integrates remote sensing, GIS-based spatial analysis, ecological modeling, and network topology assessment to achieve three primary objectives: 1) To construct an ecological network by identifying key ecological patches and corridors. 2) To optimize the connectivity of the ecological network using the Minimum Cumulative Resistance (MCR) model. 3) To improve ecological robustness and carbon sequestration capacity through topological optimization. 4) The research follows a three-phase framework, as illustrated in Figure 3, which consists of: 5) Identification of Ecological Source. 5) Construction of Ecological Network Using the Minimum Cumulative Resistance (MCR) Model. 7) Optimization of Ecological Network for Increased Robustness and Carbon Sequestration

3.2.4 Technological Roadmap

The technology roadmap (Figure 3) presents the research framework, outlining the sequential steps involved in the construction, assessment, and optimization of ecological networks. The approach is divided into three main phases, each of which contributes to the overall goal of optimizing ecological networks for sustainability and carbon sequestration.

Study Area & Research Content

Figure 3.2.4 1 The technical roadmap in the first phase of the study was to identify ecological source areas that are important for the conservation of biodiversity and ecosystem services

Chapter-IV

4. Research Methods

This chapter presents the methodological framework adopted for the construction and optimization of the Ecological Spatial Network (ESN) in the Thal Desert, Punjab, Pakistan. The approach integrates remote sensing, GIS-based spatial analysis, ecological modeling, and topological assessment to identify ecological sources, construct connectivity corridors, and optimize network robustness and carbon sequestration capacity.

The research methodology consists of three main stages: Construction of the Ecological Spatial Network (ESN) using complex network theory and spatial connectivity principles. Development of a minimum cumulative resistance (MCR) model to construct ecological corridors. Optimization of the ecological network using topological indicators and ecological function assessment. The methodology follows a technical roadmap (Figure 3 in Section 2.3) to ensure a structured and systematic research process.

4.1 Networks

4.1.1 Construction of Ecological Spatial Network

Ecological spatial networks (ESN) are a theoretical and practical framework that integrates landscape ecology, network theory, and spatial analysis to assess ecological connectivity, biodiversity conservation, and environmental stability. The approach applies complex network theory to quantify the spatial relationships between ecological components, allowing for a structured representation of landscape connectivity and functional interactions.^[98, 99]

4.1.2 Fundamentals of Ecological Spatial Networks

Ecological spatial networks (ESNs) are an advanced spatial modeling approach that uses network-based principles to simplify and quantify landscape structure, ecological interactions, and environmental controls.^[100] The method helps to gain a deeper understanding of ecosystem function by identifying ecological nodes (habitat patches) and ecological corridors (connecting pathways) within the landscape. Principles of complex network theory are used to represent the ecological structure of the landscape, allowing researchers to assess the individual components (nodes) and their interactions (edges) within the ecosystem.^[35, 46] Key features of ecological spatial networks 1) Network nodes (ecological resources): Key ecological patches, such as forests, wetlands, and grasslands, that serve as habitat resources, biodiversity reserves, and carbon sinks. 2) Network edges (ecological corridors): These corridors facilitate species migration, energy flow, and landscape connectivity by connecting dispersed ecological resources. 3) Resistance surface: The ease with which species can move across a landscape is influenced by topography, land cover, human activities, and vegetation density. Network connectivity: The strength of interactions between ecological nodes, defined by topological metrics such as degree centrality, betweenness, and proximity.

Limitations of traditional network models 1) Most existing ecological network models do not fully account for the topological features that influence ecological interactions at regional scales. Traditional habitat connectivity models are typically based on site-specific analyses, but lack spatial complexity and functional assessments. The eco-spatial network (ESN) model developed in this study overcomes these limitations by: 2) Integrating topological features to assess ecosystem connectivity. 2) Integrating spatial resistance analysis to identify the lowest cost ecological corridors. 3) Improving network robustness by optimizing ecological pathways using graph theory and resistance modeling.

4.1.3 Ecological Source Identification

Ecological resources are important components of ecological spatial networks. They are central to biodiversity, carbon sinks, and functional habitats that maintain ecosystem stability. The selection of these resources is critical to establishing efficient and resilient ecological networks, especially in arid and semi-arid regions where habitat fragmentation and land degradation pose significant challenges. ^[101, 102] These sites are essential for improving ecological conditions in arid and semi-arid regions. Representative species for each land cover type are listed in Table 2. Forest areas are limited to areas with rainfall of about 500 mm. Sites were classified according to the percentage vegetation cover (VFC): sites with a VFC below 0.15 had no significant ecological functions. Wetlands were identified by selecting water and wetland cells with a normalized difference water index (MNDWI) above 0.25 and extending their boundaries by 500 m. Wetlands have a wide range of ecological functions and are located near water bodies. ^[103]

This study identified ecological sources based on land cover types that are conducive to carbon sequestration, including forests, wetlands, and grasslands. These ecological patches are core nodes in the network, supporting species migration, nutrient cycling, and hydrological balance. To ensure scientific rigor, a multi-criteria selection method was used, combining remote sensing data, vegetation indices, and hydrological parameters.

4.1.3.1 Selection Criteria for Ecological Sources

Identify high priority ecological resources, the following selection criteria were used: 1) Vegetation Cover (VFC): Plots with $VFC > 0.15$ were considered ecologically functional areas. Areas with VFC below 0.15 were excluded due to low vegetation density and minimal ecological significance. 2) Forest precipitation threshold: Forest area was restricted to areas with annual precipitation of at least 500 mm. This ensured that a stable, moisture-retaining forest ecosystem could develop in arid areas. 3) Wetland Improvement Normalized Difference Water Index (MNDWI): $MNDWI > 0.25$ was used to identify wetland areas. A 500-meter buffer was established around wetlands to account for hydrological connectivity and seasonal variability. 3) Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) for grasslands: Grasslands with $NDVI > 40\%$ indicated good vegetation cover. A 50-meter buffer was used to improve connectivity between patches. These selection criteria ensured the identification of ecological areas with high conservation value, which formed the basis of the Ecological Spatial Network (ESN).

4.1.3.2 Classification of Ecological Sources in the Thal Desert

The ecological resources of the Thal Desert can be divided into three main categories: 1) Forest areas – carbon sinks and biodiversity reserves. 2) Wetlands and water bodies – hydrologically active areas that support species migration. 2) Grasslands – soil stabilizers and primary producers in the ecosystem. Specific selection thresholds and representative species were assigned to each category to ensure consistency with regional biodiversity characteristics.

Table 4.1.3.2 1 Criteria for evaluating ecological patches and their target species.

Types of Patches	Target Species in Thal	Total area Threshold (Km2)	Criteria/Additional Metrics
Forest Patches	Acacia Senegal, Prosopis cineraria (Jand) Date Palm (Phoenix dactylifera), Ziziphus mauritiana (Ber), Tamarix aphylla (Farash), Wan (Salvadora oleoides), Desert Marigold (Baileya multiradiata), Salsola spp. (Prickly Russian Thistle)	10	N/L
Water and wet patch-es	Fimbristylis dichotoma, Cyperus rotundus, Phragmites karka, Typha spp. Arthrocnemum indicum, Saccharum spontaneum, Saccharum bengalense, Suaeda fruticosa	20	MNDWI > 0.25 and buffered 70m outwards
Grassland Patches	Cenchrus ciliaris (Dhaman Grass), Lasiurus scindicus (Sewan Grass), Saccharum bengalense (Munji Grass), Cymbopogon jwarancusa (Khabal Grass), Panicum turgidum (Bhurt Grass), Desmostachya bipinnata (Dab Grass), Leptochloa fusca (Kallar Grass)	15	NDVI-based Grass cover > 40%, buffered 50 m outwards

4.1.3.3 Methodology for Ecological Source Identification

Identification of ecological resources was performed using remote sensing, GIS-based spatial analysis, and vegetation index modeling. The methodology included the following steps: 1) Data collection and preprocessing: MODIS land cover data (MCD12Q1.061) was used for vegetation type classification. NDVI, MNDWI, and VFC indices were extracted using Google Earth Engine (GEE). Digital elevation models (DEMs) and precipitation data were analyzed to assess forest survival areas. 2) Land cover classification A supervised classification method was used in ArcGIS and GEE to classify the study area into forest, wetland, and grassland. Ground observations and high-resolution images were used to validate the classified land cover types. 3) Vegetation and hydrological index analysis NDVI, MNDWI, and VFC values were extracted to classify low, medium, and high vegetation cover areas. A threshold-based segmentation method was used to separate high-priority ecological patches. 4) Buffering and spatial adjustment A 500-meter buffer was set for wetland patches to account for hydrological changes. Grassland patches were extended by 50 meters to improve connectivity and biodiversity support. 5) Validation and refinement Classification patches were cross-validated with high-resolution satellite imagery to ensure accuracy. Areas with incorrect vegetation cover classification were manually corrected. This systematic identification process ensured that high-quality ecological resources were accurately delineated and formed the backbone of the ecological network.

4.1.3.4 Integration of Ecological Sources into Network Construction

Once ecological sources were identified, they were incorporated into the ecological spatial network as nodes, forming the primary components of the connectivity model. These nodes were further analyzed to: Assess their ecological functionality based on biomass, vegetation health, and carbon sequestration potential. Evaluate their connectivity potential using graph-theoretical analysis to quantify network resilience. Determine their role in ecological corridors, ensuring efficient species dispersal and environmental sustainability. This structured methodology allows for scientific prioritization of conservation areas, supporting climate adaptation and biodiversity management strategies.

4.2 Construction of an Ecological Corridor

Ecological corridors are important connecting points of ecological resources. They promote species migration, gene exchange and energy flow within ecological spatial networks. ^[104, 105] These corridors enhance landscape connectivity, reduce the impacts of habitat fragmentation, and ensure the stability of ecosystem functions. In semi-arid areas such as the Thal Desert, where human activities and climate change affect biodiversity, identifying and building effective ecological corridors is critical for sustainable land management and conservation planning. The Minimum Cumulative Resistance (MCR) model is applied to identify optimal ecological corridors by analyzing the least resistance paths for species migration and material flows. This approach takes into account multiple environmental and anthropogenic resistance factors, ensuring data-driven corridor planning ^[37].

4.2.1 Minimum Cumulative Resistance (MCR) Model for Corridor Identification

Minimum cumulative resistance (MCR) models are widely used in landscape ecology and conservation planning to simulate species movement and ecological connectivity [106]. The model integrates three main components: 1) Ecological resources: the main habitat patches identified in Section

4.2.1.2 Resistance surfaces

Indicates the difficulty of moving over different terrains. 3) Path of least resistance: Identifies the best corridors for improving ecological resilience. MCR is calculated using the following formula [107]. However, we believe that the traditional MCR model does not take into account the impact of different land use types on the landscape resistance values at different intensities of human development, which hinders the process of ecological energy flow. The MCR value is calculated using the following formula:[108, 109], as follows:

$$MCR = f_{min} \sum_{j=n}^{i=m} (D_{ij} \times R_i) \quad (1)$$

where function f represents the positive correlation between basic landscape characteristics and distance to a source of minimum resistance, and min represents the minimum cumulative resistance experienced when transforming from landscape unit i to source unit j . D_{ij} [109] represents the spatial separation between landscape cell i and source cell j ; R_i is the drag coefficient during the transition from landscape cell i to source cell j . Using the pixel representation of nodes and links, the cumulative distance between the drag surface and the nearest source can be calculated.

4.2.2 Least-Cost Path Analysis for Corridor Mapping

The resistance values obtained in Table 3 were used in a least cost path (LCP) analysis in ArcGIS 10.8 to identify the best ecological corridors. The LCP algorithm calculates the least resistance route to ensure that species can efficiently cross the landscape. The node value represents the distance of the landscape unit, and the node direction represents the direction of ecological flow.[107, 110]. the total resistance (A) to motion across resistance surface is calculated as follows:

$$A = \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=0}^n (C_i - C_{i+1} + 1) \right. \quad (2a)$$

$$A = \left\{ \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \sum_{i=0}^n (C_i - C_{i+1} + 1) \right. \quad (2b)$$

Where n is the total number of pixels, C_i represents the value of a single pixel, C_{i+1} is the consumption value along the direction of movement, and A represents the total cost of the source at a specific price. (b) and (a) are applied when the surface passes through pixels diagonally and moves vertically or horizontally, respectively. The diversity of each ecological source is determined by its unique ecological energy. The modified form of the ecological land growth model is designed by four factors: basic resistivity characteristics, distance, source type, and source level. The updated formula is expressed as follows:

$$MCRP = f_{min} \sum_{j=n}^{i=m} (D_{ij} \times R_i \times P_j) \quad (3)$$

In the formula, the relative energy factor of source j is represented by Pj. The larger the Pj value is, the higher the energy factor of the ecological source is ^[54].

4.2.3 Resistance Surface and Factor Selection

The resistance surface represents the difficulty of species to move through the landscape, under the influence of natural and anthropogenic factors. Twelve major resistance factors were included in the study (Table 3), categorized as: Topographic features: elevation (DEM) and slope. Vegetation index: NDVI (vegetation health), VFC (vegetation cover). Hydrological factors: MNDWI (water availability). Human interference: road density, population density and land use intensity. Resistance values were assigned using the ArcGIS Natural Breakpoint (NBM) method, classifying each factor into five categories. The Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) was used to assign weights to each factor to ensure the scientific prioritization of ecological mobility constraints.

Table 4.2.3 1 Resistance Factors and Weights Assigned in MCR Model

Factor	Weight	Grade	Value	Factor	Weight	Grade	Value
DEM	0.01	1	63 - 230	Night Light	0.05	1	0.02-1.75
		5	230 - 411			5	1.75- 10.06
		10	411 - 641			10	10.06- 29.06
		15	641. - 851			15	29.06- 76.56
		20	851- 1518			20	76.56- 151.38
Slope	0.04	20	0 - 2.3535	VFC	0.16	1	0 - 0.16
		15	2.33- 6.47			5	0.16- 0.38
		10	6.47- 14.41			10	0.58 - 0.80
		5	14.41- 25.59			15	0.58 - 0.80
		20	25.59- 75.02			20	0.8078 - 1

NDVI	0.6	1	0.42-0.02	Population Density	0.06	1	90 - 205	
		5	0.02-0.17			-	5	205 - 274
		10	0.17-0.29			-	10	274 - 333
		15	0.29-0.41			-	15	333 - 482
		20	0.41-0.74			-	20	482 - 813
MNDWI	0.12	1	0.51-0.29	Land Surface Temperature	0.19	1	14- 15	
		5	0.29-0.17			-	5	15- 15.16
		10	0.17-0.06			-	10	15.16- 15.26
		15	0.06-0.36			-	15	15.22 - 15.38
		20	0.36-0.77			-	20	15.38 - 15.50
Road Density	0.03	20	0 - 3.44	Distance Settlement	0.4	1	0 - 24,669	
		15	3.44-6.88			-	5	24,66- 49,33
		10	6.88-10.32			-	10	49.33 - 74.01
		5	10.32-13.77			-	15	74.01 - 98.67
		1	13.77-17.21			-	20	98.7 - 123
Water Density	0.08	1	0.01-0.16	LULC	0.28	1	Forest Land	
		5	0.16-0.38			5	Shrubland	

10	0.38- 0.58		10	Grassland
15	0.58- 0.80		15	Water- Wetland
20	0.8078- 1		20	Barren land

4.3 Topological Indicators for Optimizing Spatial Network

This is an overall architecture of an ecological network, a combination of complex network theory and graph theory, and a study of the topological characteristics and optimization of ecological networks (ESNs). Topological indicators are key to network structure and contribute to the improvement of network connectivity, functionality, and function. Topological structure, regional distribution, cluster efficiency, betweenness centrality and coreness, individuality, and ecological stability are all of our concerns.^[111, 112] These metrics provide valuable insights for optimizing ecological corridors and enhancing network robustness.

4.3.1 Degree

The degree of a node in a network represents the number of direct connections it has to other nodes. It is a basic measure of node importance, indicating which ecological patches play a crucial role in maintaining network connectivity. Higher values indicate that the node is well-connected and can serve as an important ecological hub. Conversely, lower degrees indicate that the node is more isolated and may be at risk of splitting. Degree Distribution in Ecological Networks Degree distribution follows different patterns in different network types: Scale-free networks: These exhibit a power-law degree distribution, in which a small number of highly connected hubs dominate. Random network: Follows a Poisson degree distribution, in which most nodes have a similar number of connections. Normal network: Displays a delta function distribution in which every node has approximately the same degree. In eco-spatial networks, understanding the degree distribution can help identify highly connected ecological patches and plan strategic interventions to improve connectivity. The network diameter indicates the maximum distance between nodes and is an important measure of connectivity throughout the network.^[41, 62, 70]

4.3.2 Clustering coefficient

The clustering coefficient quantifies the degree of connectivity between a node's neighbors. It measures the probability that two nodes connected to a common node are also connected, creating triangular relationships within the network. A higher clustering coefficient indicates better local connectivity, suggesting a more compact and functionally consistent ecological network. Conversely, a lower clustering coefficient may indicate a greater degree of network fragmentation, which may lead to reduced ecological resilience^[37]. The clustering coefficient C_a is expressed as:

$$C_a = \frac{E_a}{C_{ka}^2} \quad (4)$$

where C_a is the clustering coefficient of node a, E_a denotes the actual number of edges among node a and its neighbors, C_{ka}^2 denotes the total number of edges among node a and its neighbors when they are all connected to each other.

A high clustering coefficient indicates a well-structured network with strong local connectivity. This is particularly important in ecological networks, as species interactions and habitat connectivity depend on the strength of local connections.

4.3.3 Betweenness

Betweenness centrality measures how often a node appears on the shortest path between other nodes in the network. It reflects the influence of a node in controlling ecological flows and determines its importance in maintaining connectivity. Nodes with high betweenness centrality act as key corridors or stepping stone habitats, facilitating species movement, nutrient exchange, and energy transfer. If these nodes are lost, the overall connectivity of the network may be severely affected.

4.3.4 Ecological Significance of Betweenness Centrality

Betweenness centrality measures how often a node appears on the shortest path between other nodes in the network. It reflects the influence of a node in controlling ecological flows and determines its importance in maintaining connectivity. Nodes with high betweenness centrality serve as important corridors or stepping-stone habitats, facilitating species migration, nutrient exchange, and energy transfer. If these nodes are lost, the overall connectivity of the network will be severely affected [53].

4.3.5 Coreness

Coreness is a quantitative measure of network hierarchy that represents how deeply a node is embedded in the network. It helps identify structurally important nodes that form the backbone of the network. The k-core of a network is the subnetwork obtained by recursively removing nodes with a degree less than k. The coreness value (k) of a node determines: The depth of the node in the ecological network. Its importance in maintaining connectivity. Its ability to resist fragmentation. Nodes with high coreness values are critical to network stability, ensuring that the core network can still function even if some peripheral nodes are lost. Ecological network optimization applications should protect and strengthen high-coreness nodes to maintain landscape integrity. Low-coreness nodes should be connected to stronger nodes to improve overall network resilience. Coreness analysis helps prioritize conservation efforts and ensure the long-term sustainability of ecological networks.

4.3.5.1 Integration of Topological Indicators for Network Optimization

The above topological indicators provide a comprehensive framework for optimizing ecological spatial networks: 1) Degree centrality: Identify key ecological nodes that need to be protected and strengthened. 2) Clustering coefficient: Determine the strength of local connectivity and guide efforts to improve corridor stability. 3) Moderate centrality: Highlight

key corridors that must be preserved to maintain species migration. 2) Simplicity: Evaluate the network hierarchy to ensure that key ecological nodes remain functional. By analyzing these indicators, targeted interventions can be designed: Strengthen ecological corridors in fragmented landscapes. Strengthen nodes with high interstitial properties to avoid connectivity interruptions. Improve local connectivity by increasing clustering coefficient values. Protect high core nodes to maintain overall network stability.

4.4 Ecological Network Gravity

4.4.1 Theoretical Basis of the Ecological Gravity Model

Conceptual Framework In ecological network analysis, gravity models are used to quantify the strength of interactions between ecological nodes, providing insights into: The strength of species movement and ecological flows between habitat patches. The potential for connectivity between ecological resources within a landscape. The effects of distance and habitat quality on spatial interactions. Ecological gravity follows the principle that the strength of interactions between two ecological patches is proportional to ecological quality and inversely proportional to cumulative resistance distance. Different ecological sites contribute differently to the ecological importance of network connectivity. Forests, wetlands, and grasslands are assigned different weights based on their carbon sequestration and potential to support species migration. Gravity models are derived from Newton's law of universal gravitation and are widely used in the study of spatial interactions to assess relationships between objects, regions, or systems. Different ecological sites contribute differently to the ecological importance of network connectivity. Forests, wetlands, and grasslands are assigned different weights based on their carbon sequestration and potential to support species migration. Gravity models are derived from Newton's law of universal gravitation and are widely used in the study of spatial interactions to assess relationships between objects, regions, or systems.^[113] The model was initially applied to city system interactions, trade flows, and regional connectivity^[65, 114-117]. The gravitational model for the ecological spatial network is presented as follows:

$$F_{ij} = G \frac{a_i m_i a_j m_j}{D_{ij}^2} \quad (5)$$

Here, F_{ij} represents the gravitational force between source i and source j in the ecological spatial network. D_{ij}^2 represents the distance between the source patches i and j . a_i, a_j represents the type of the ecological source patches i and j . m_i, m_j represents the ecological quality of the source patches i and j . G is a constant that scales the gravitational force in the ecological spatial network model^[118, 119].

4.4.2 Modification of the Gravity Model for Desert Ecosystems

Challenges of applying traditional gravity models to ecological networks Traditional gravity models mainly focus on urban systems, economic connections, and trade relations. However, applying this model to ecological networks, especially in desert environments, requires modifications to consider ecosystem dynamics: 1) Incorporate cumulative resistance distance 2) Unlike standard Euclidean distance, cumulative resistance distance (D_{ij}^2) takes into account terrain complexity, vegetation density, and human disturbance. 2) This will

truly restore the ecological connectivity of desert landscapes. Adjusted ecological quality indicators ($m_i, m_{jm_i}, m_{jmi}, m_j$) In desert ecosystems, the ecological value of a site is affected by soil stability, water availability, vegetation health, and climatic conditions. To determine ecological quality, we used vegetation indices (NDVI, VFC), biodiversity richness, and habitat suitability models. Ecological source classification ($a_i, a_{ja_i}, a_{jai}, a_j$)

4.4.3 Application of Ecological Gravity for Network Optimization

Prioritize high gravity corridors. 2) Corridors with high F_{ij} ^[109] F_{ij} values are prioritized in conservation and preservation efforts. 3) The pathways act as powerful ecological highways, allowing species to migrate unhindered. 4) Identify ecological barriers Low-gravity connections highlight ecological barriers caused by human disturbance, dry areas or habitat degradation. Targeted restoration measures (afforestation, wetland restoration) can improve ecological interactions. Improving strategic corridors allows new corridors to be designed and optimized by adjusting aerodynamic drag coefficients and improving ecological stepping stones. This allows isolated areas to be integrated into larger ecological spatial networks.

4.4.4 Significance of Ecological Gravity Model in Desert Ecosystems

Applying gravity models to desert ecological networks can: 1) improve understanding of ecological interactions based on science-based connectivity modeling. 2) quantify spatial relationships to guide conservation strategies at the landscape level. 3) identify ecological hotspots and barriers for targeted management actions. 4) optimize biodiversity corridors to ensure long-term ecosystem resilience. By combining ecological gravity analysis with network topology assessment (Section 3.2), an integrated framework for ecological connectivity planning was created.

4.5 EFCT optimization model

The Ecological Functionality-Connectivity-Topology (EFCT) Optimization Model is a systematic framework for enhancing ecological functions and spatial connectivity by optimizing landscape structure and ecological networks. The model integrates spatial analysis, ecological function assessment, and topological modeling to identify deficient areas and implement targeted interventions to improve the network and achieve sustainability. To achieve an optimal ecological spatial network, the following are required: Maximize carbon sequestration through functional landscape configuration. Improve ecological connectivity to promote species migration and biodiversity conservation. Reduce fragmentation by introducing stepping stones and ecological corridors. The EFCT model applies these principles to classify landscape areas according to ecological functions and connectivity, and deploy appropriate optimization strategies to improve ecological resilience and network efficiency. ^[120].

4.5.1 Core Components of the EFCT Model

The EFCT optimization model is based on three core components: 1) Ecological function (EF), which represents the carbon sequestration potential, biodiversity richness, and habitat quality of ecological patches. Areas with higher ecological functions contribute more to ecosystem stability. 2) Connectivity (C) measures the degree of connectivity between ecological patches and their role in species migration and material flow. Higher connectivity can improve

ecological interactions, while lower connectivity can lead to habitat fragmentation and isolation. 3) Topological optimization uses network theory and spatial modeling to identify the structural role of nodes and corridors in ecological networks. Enhance the resilience of the landscape by adding or reinforcing stepping stones and walkways. By integrating these three components, the EFCT model provides a strategic decision-making framework for improving ecological networks.

4.5.1.1 Classification of Optimization Zones

The EFCT model divides ecological patches into three categories based on their function-connectivity relationship (Figure 4): 1) Areas with high connectivity and low functionality These areas have strong spatial connectivity, but lack ecological functions (degraded land in a well-connected network). 2) Optimization strategy: Increase vegetation cover through reforestation or natural regeneration. Improve water retention and soil quality, and support habitat restoration. Strengthen ecosystem protection policies to prevent further degradation. 3) Areas with high functionality and low connectivity These areas have high ecological function, but the landscape is fragmented, limiting species distribution and ecosystem integration. 4) Optimization strategy: Develop ecological corridors to connect isolated patches. Build windbreaks and buffer zones to improve spatial connectivity. Create artificial stepping stones to improve habitat connectivity. 5) Areas with low functionality and low connectivity These areas are the most critical for intervention because they lack both functionality and connectivity. Optimization strategy: Restore habitat functions by improving ecological productivity (wetland restoration, grassland restoration). Place stepping stones to facilitate species migration and nutrient flow. Build ecological corridors and strengthen network integration.

4.5.1.2 EFCT Optimization Model Workflow

The EFCT optimization model uses a stepwise approach to identify and improve ecological networks (Figure 4). Step 1: Evaluate the relationship between ecological function and connectivity Calculate the ecological function-connectivity (EFC) value for each ecological patch. Classify patches according to feature-connectivity synergy. Identify areas that need to enhance connectivity, enhance functionality, or both. Step 2: Prioritize optimization strategies For areas with high connectivity but low functionality, focus on functional improvements. For areas with high functionality and low connectivity, prioritize connectivity improvements. For areas with low functionality and low connectivity, implement joint restoration strategies. Step 3: Implement network optimization measures to increase vegetation cover and water retention capacity by 10% and improve ecological function. Introduce stepping stones to improve network cohesion and ecological interactions. Develop ecological corridors using the minimum distance growth (MDG) model to maintain spatial balance. Step 4: Optimize network structure Limit the number of stepping stones to 20% of the total number of nodes to maintain spatial efficiency. Limit the proportion of new additions to ecological corridors to less than 20%, and prioritize short-distance connections. Step 5: Model validation and performance evaluation Use spatial simulation and ecological modeling tools (ArcGIS, Python, Gephi) to evaluate network efficiency. Validate optimization results based on improvements in connectivity, ecological function, and carbon sequestration capacity.

4.5.4 Visualization and Mapping of EFCT Optimization Outputs

The EFCT model was implemented using GIS-based analysis, remote sensing, and network topology modeling: ArcGIS and Google Earth Engine (GEE): for spatial analysis and classification of ecological patches. Python-based network modeling: for assessing topological properties and connectivity strength. Graph-based visualization tools (Gephi, MATLAB): for generating spatial network topology maps. Figure 4 visually represents the EFCT optimization process and illustrates classification, prioritization, and strategic interventions in the ecological network.

4.5.5 Application of EFCT Model in Desert Ecosystems

The EFCT optimization model is particularly useful for semi-arid and desert ecosystems, such as the Thal Desert. These ecosystems have limited vegetation cover and require targeted reforestation and land reclamation. Hydrological connectivity is poor, requiring wetland restoration and water resource management. Landscape fragmentation disrupts ecological interactions, making corridor development and incremental interventions essential. By enhancing ecological functions and improving connectivity, the EFCT model promotes long-term sustainability and resilience of arid landscapes.

4.5.6 Expected Benefits and Implications of the EFCT Model

The EFCT optimization model provides a scientific and systematic approach to strengthen ecological networks by improving key connectivity routes. Improve habitat function through targeted carbon sequestration strategies. Reduce landscape fragmentation and ensure the long-term sustainability of ecosystems. Strengthen biodiversity conservation and support species migration and gene exchange. Support climate adaptation and spatial planning by making data-driven recommendations. By integrating spatial modeling, ecological function assessment, and topological network analysis, the EFCT model becomes an important tool for sustainable landscape management and conservation planning.

Figure 4.5.6 1 Conceptual Flow Chart illustrating the optimization model for EFCT

4.6 Calculating Carbon Sequestration Accuracy

Carbon sequestration plays a vital role in mitigating climate change by absorbing and storing carbon dioxide through natural ecosystems such as forests, grasslands, wetlands and water bodies. It therefore helps balance the carbon concentration in the atmosphere. To achieve carbon neutrality, accurate estimates of carbon sources and sinks are needed to ensure that net emissions reach zero [121, 122]. Although several studies have evaluated the carbon absorption capacity of different ecosystems in China and around the world, [123, 124], In this study, carbon sequestration calculations are applied to the Thal Desert in Punjab Province, Pakistan. The objectives are to quantify the potential of different land uses as carbon sinks, to analyze trends in carbon sequestration, and to evaluate the role of ecological restoration measures in enhancing carbon storage in dry environments.

4.6.1 Method for Calculating Carbon Sequestration

4.6.1.1 Carbon Sink Estimation Model

The total carbon sequestration capacity (C_t) of the study area is calculated based on Land Use Land Cover (LULC) patterns using the following formula:

$$C_t = \sum_{i=1}^n A_i S_i \quad (6)$$

In this equation, C_t represents the total quantity of carbon sink, i is the land use type, A is the land area, and S is the carbon sink coefficient (t/hm²a).

4.6.1.2 Carbon Sequestration Coefficient

The carbon sequestration coefficient (SiSiSi) represents the carbon storage capacity of different land types and is derived from existing literature and empirical studies.^[86, 125-128], Table 4 presents the carbon sequestration coefficients for various land use types used in this study.

Table 4.6.1.2 1 Carbon sequestration coefficient for various land use categories.

Land Use Type	Carbon Sequestration Coefficient (t/hm ² a)	Justification Literature
Forestland	0.69	[123]
Watershed	0.49	[129]
Wetland	0.35	[129]

To estimate the distribution of carbon sequestration in the Thal Desert, we used a spatial analysis approach: Step 1: LULC classification Land use categories were extracted using the MODIS MCD12Q1 land cover dataset (2001-2022). Classification accuracy was assessed using ground truthing and remote sensing validation techniques. Step 2: Assignment of carbon sequestration factors Carbon sequestration factors were assigned to each land use type according to Table 4. Coefficient values were obtained from peer-reviewed ecological studies and regional adaptation assessments. Step 3: GIS-based carbon sink calculations. Carbon sequestration was estimated by multiplying the land surface raster by the carbon sequestration factor raster using ArcGIS raster calculations. A carbon storage map was created to visualize areas with high storage capacity and low carbon emissions. Step 4: Statistical validation and accuracy assessment Comparative analysis was performed with existing literature to validate the carbon estimates. Sensitivity analysis ensured that changes in land use change were incorporated into the carbon sequestration model.

4.6.1.3 Regional Carbon Sequestration Trends in the Thal Desert

Preliminary findings from the carbon sequestration assessment indicate the following trends: Forest patches serve as primary carbon sinks, accounting for the highest carbon sequestration rates (0.69 t/hm²). Grasslands and shrublands provide moderate sequestration capacity, playing a critical role in maintaining regional carbon balance. Wetlands contribute significantly to carbon storage, but their fragmentation reduces their sequestration potential. Cultivated lands and barren lands exhibit the lowest sequestration potential, making them priority areas for ecological restoration efforts. These findings emphasize the importance of protecting and expanding high-carbon sequestration zones, particularly forests and wetlands.

4.6.1.4 Application of Carbon Sequestration Analysis in Desert Ecosystem Restoration

Carbon sequestration estimates can be used to: Guide afforestation and reforestation projects by identifying priority areas for afforestation and vegetation restoration. Support wetland conservation efforts to improve water retention and carbon sequestration capacity. Develop sustainable land use policies and integrate carbon sequestration considerations into regional

planning. Increase vegetation cover on bare and degraded lands and reduce the effects of desertification. Contribute to global efforts to mitigate climate change by incorporating carbon sequestration modeling into conservation strategies.

4.6.1.5 Implications for Climate Policy and Land Management

Carbon sequestration models can contribute to national carbon neutrality goals and ensure effective land management and ecosystem protection policies. Desert ecosystems have enormous potential for carbon sequestration, underscoring the need to develop long-term ecological protection strategies. Accurate carbon accounting is essential for climate finance, as it allows regions such as the Thal Desert to participate in carbon credit markets and environmental offset programs.

4.7 Robustness of Ecological Spatial Network

Ecological spatial networks (ESNs) in arid environments are important components of landscape stability and ecosystem resilience. Structural configuration directly affects how well the land can recover from environmental disturbances, human activities, and desertification. The robustness of ESNs can be assessed by examining their structural resilience, which determines their ability to absorb shocks, maintain functionality, and recover from disruptions [130].

4.7.1 Key Challenges Affecting ESN Robustness

Anthropogenic disturbances: Urban expansion, overgrazing, deforestation, and land conversion degrade ecological corridors and nodes, reducing network resilience. Desertification and climate change: Extreme temperatures, shifting dunes, and prolonged droughts fragment ecological connectivity and disrupt biodiversity corridors. Targeted versus random disturbances: Targeted attacks on high-value ecological nodes (primary habitat patches) cause severe disruptions. Random disturbances (natural erosion or stochastic climate events) create fragmentation but at a lower impact. The primary drivers of this network degradation are anthropogenic activities and desertification, resulting in the depletion of ecological nodes and corridors. Despite being a natural and unpredictable phenomenon, desertification is intentionally and detrimentally caused by human intervention. The danger posed by targeted attacks on high-value nodes surpasses that of random attacks due to the more conspicuous nature of their consequences [131]. This study quantifies and optimizes the structural robustness of the Thal Desert ESN by simulating network failures and resilience strategies. The aim is to ensure long-term sustainability and functional connectivity.

4.7.2 Evaluating the Robustness of the Ecological Spatial Network

Structural resilience assessments examine the structural integrity of ecological networks by assessing the ability of networks to maintain connectivity after nodes are removed. Key indicators of robustness include: Network connectivity: measures the extent of ecological corridors and their ability to connect habitat nodes. Node and edge redundancy: ensures that alternative paths are available in the event of a disruption. Effects of fragmentation: assessing how network degradation affects species movement.

4.7.3 Network Vulnerability to Disturbances

ESNs encounter two types of disturbances: Random disturbances: caused by natural disasters, random climate events, or uncontrolled land degradation. Targeted disturbances: intentional destruction of high-value nodes by human pressures, infrastructure development, and land use changes. Targeted attacks have significantly higher impacts than random disturbances because they eliminate key ecological nodes at the level of major corridors [130, 132]. We take an integrated approach to assess and optimize the structural integrity of the eco-spatial network in the Thal Desert. The first step is to construct an adjacency matrix that accurately describes the complex relationships within the network. In this study, we used MatlabR2023 software to simplify the network into an unconstrained topological graph. The model was then tested against random and targeted perturbations to determine its robustness. This holistic approach analyzes the strengths and weaknesses of the network, provides valuable insights into optimization requirements, and ensures long-term sustainability against potential risks [54].

Adjacency Matrix Construction for Network Analysis An adjacency matrix was constructed to represent the connectivity between ecological nodes and corridors. This matrix was used to simulate network failures and determine the network's ability to withstand node loss.

4.7.4 Methodology for ESN Robustness Analysis

This study used MATLAB R2023 software to simulate the Thal Desert ESN as a topological graph in order to evaluate the network's resiliency. Step 1: Simulation and Network Building A topological graph was created by simplifying the ecological network, where: Ecological resources (grasslands, marshes, and forests) are represented by nodes. Corridors between nodes are represented by edges. Network disruption: Random node removal mimicked natural deterioration. Deliberate habitat destruction was emulated by the targeted removal of nodes. Step 2: Network resilience calculation. Following the destruction of some network components, the system was examined to determine whether the nodes and edges that had been lost could be recovered. The following formula was used to determine the resilience ratio (RRR):

$$R = \frac{C}{(N - N_r)} \quad (7)$$

In the above formula, N represents the original size of the network, N_r represents the number of ecological nodes removed, and C represents the number of nodes in the largest connected subgraph of the ecological network. Step 3: Optimize and strengthen the ecological network Based on the resilience score, we implement targeted interventions to strengthen the ecological network. Strategies include adding stepping stones to repair damaged corridors. Improving edge redundancy to create alternative paths. Reforesting degraded nodes to improve network resilience.

4.7.5 Impact of Network Disturbances on Ecological Stability

Results of random and targeted attacks. Random attacks can gradually fragment the network, but the network remains partially connected. Targeted attacks on valuable nodes can cause severe ecosystem collapse, disrupting the movement of biodiversity and habitat connectivity. Highly connected hubs play a critical role in maintaining network integrity. Ecological consequences of network degradation the loss of important corridors can lead to: Reduced

species migration and gene flow. Habitat isolation and ecosystem fragmentation are increasing. Ecosystem degradation leads to reduced carbon sequestration potential.

4.7.6 Strategies to Improve Network Robustness

Based on the network resilience analysis, the following key optimization strategies are proposed: 1. Strengthen ecological nodes and corridors. Improve habitat connectivity by developing new ecological corridors. Increase vegetation coverage around degraded nodes and restore ecosystem functions. Prioritize the protection of valuable ecological nodes and reduce their vulnerability. Redundancy and stepping stone implementation Introduce stepping stone patches to strengthen scattered connections. Use hierarchical ecological network design to optimize landscape connectivity. Add edge redundancy to ensure that backup paths are available in the event of failure. Adaptive management strategies formulate land use policies that minimize human interference. Use remote sensing and GIS tools to monitor ecological networks. Implement restoration plans to reverse environmental degradation. A robustness analysis of the Thal Desert ecological network shows the importance of preserving valuable ecological nodes and corridors. Targeted attacks can cause major damage and require a proactive protection strategy. Optimizing network resilience will ensure long-term ecosystem sustainability and climate resilience. Future research directions. Integrate AI-based cyber resilience models for real-time impact assessment. Apply machine learning algorithms to predict future network vulnerabilities. Integrate socio-economic factors into network perturbation models.

4.7.7 Summary of this chapter

Chapter 4 presents the research methods used to analyze and optimize the Thal Desert Ecological Spatial Network (ESN), with a particular focus on improving ecological connectivity, carbon sequestration, and overall ecosystem resilience. This chapter introduces the main methods and models for constructing and optimizing ESNs and assessing their robustness and contribution to climate change mitigation. This chapter first discusses the basic principles of the Ecological Spatial Network (ESN). This provides a conceptual framework for understanding the importance of ecological connectivity and the role of spatial networks in ecosystem health. Ecological corridor construction is an important initiative to connect ecological places. The minimum cumulative resistance (MCR) model is used to identify corridors. This model can identify the paths with the least resistance to ecological flow and promote the establishment of seamless networks that support biodiversity, resource flow, and energy exchange. Next, topological indicators such as degree, clustering coefficient, betweenness, and coreness are introduced as key indicators for optimizing spatial networks. These indicators help evaluate the importance of individual nodes in the network and their connections. They help identify strategic nodes and corridors that need to be improved to enhance ecological functions. By incorporating these topological indicators into network optimization, ecological networks can become more efficient and stable. This is essential for long-term ecological health and resilience.

The gravity model of ecological networks is also discussed and specifically applied to desert ecosystems. The model measures the strength of connections between ecological nodes, taking

into account both ecological quality and distance. The modified gravity model provides valuable insights into how to improve the distribution and connectivity of ecological patches to facilitate better energy and material flows. The chapter also presents the EFCT optimization model, which integrates carbon sequestration calculations into the spatial network optimization process. This approach ensures that improvements in network functionality and connectivity directly contribute to improved carbon storage in the landscape. Next steps for the research include validating carbon sequestration maps using field data, assessing the long-term effects of land use change on carbon stocks, and further refining carbon sequestration estimates using advanced remote sensing techniques such as LiDAR and hyperspectral analysis. Finally, the robustness of ecological spatial networks is assessed, focusing on the ability of networks to withstand and recover from disturbances. This analysis is critical to determine the resilience of networks to external shocks, such as the effects of climate change or anthropogenic disturbances, and to guide future conservation strategies aimed at enhancing ecological stability.

Chapter 4 provides a comprehensive overview of methods for optimizing ESNs, with a particular focus on enhancing carbon sequestration, improving connectivity, and increasing network robustness. The research approaches discussed are critical to achieving the research goals of improving the ecological health of Thal Desert and contributing to broader climate resilience and carbon neutrality goals.

Chapter-V

5. Results

5.1 Extraction and Analysis of Ecological Spatial Network

5.1.1 Screening of Ecological Sources

In this study, the main objective was to identify and assess ecological source patches in the Thal Desert using long-term land use land cover (LULC) data. These sites play a vital role in maintaining the ecological functions of the region, particularly in terms of carbon sequestration, energy flow, and species migration. Identification of these sites is essential for constructing an eco-spatial network (ESN) that represents the spatial distribution and interconnection of important ecological nodes and corridors.

5.1.1.1 Ecological Source Patches Identification

The ecological source areas in the Thal Desert are mainly classified into two types: forests and wetlands. Forests are the main ecological feature of the study area and cover most of the desert, especially in areas such as Mianwali and Kushab. These lands are of great ecological importance as they are excellent sites for carbon sequestration and biodiversity conservation. The total area of forests studied is 47.7144 square kilometers, which contributes greatly to the carbon sequestration capacity of desert ecosystems. In addition to forests, wetlands were also found, with higher density in the northwestern part of the Thal Desert, especially along the Jhelum River. These wetlands are characterized by inland lakes, ponds and other water bodies that play a vital role in the functioning of the ecosystem. Wetlands are often rich in biodiversity, contribute to nutrient cycling, water purification and provide important habitat for various species.

5.1.1.2 Fragmentation of Forest Patches

A key finding from the analysis was the discontinuity of forested areas, especially in Bhakkar, Kushab, Mianwali, Jain, Laiyah, Muzaffargarh, and several urban areas. This fragmentation leads to ecological isolation, limiting species migration and energy and material exchange in the landscape. These fragmented areas reduce the overall carbon sequestration potential of the desert and affect the overall integrity and functioning of the ecosystem. The Multiscale Polygon Analysis (MSPA) approach was used to identify not only large continuous ecological patches but also smaller, dispersed patches that act as stepping stones in the landscape. Stepping stones are important in maintaining ecological connectivity between isolated areas, providing pathways for species migration, and facilitating the flow of nutrients across fragmented landscapes.

5.1.1.3 Ecological Source Patch Classification

Based on the findings, the eco-source areas were categorized as follows: Forest areas: These areas are mainly located in Mianwali and Kushab and are the backbone of the carbon sequestration potential of the Thal Desert. Wetlands: These areas are mainly located in the northwest, especially around the Jhelum River. They are essential for biodiversity and form

Results

important nodes in the network. A total of 76 eco-source areas were identified, including 56 forest areas and 20 wetlands. These sites are scattered across the desert landscape and form the basis for constructing an eco-spatial network (ESN), which we will analyze below.

Figure 5.1.1.3 1 Construction of ecological source patches (a) and ecological spatial network (b) in the Thal Desert (a) Ecological source patches

5.1.1.4 Interpretation of Results

Results from the ecological source area screening revealed that forested areas are the main contributors to carbon sinks and biodiversity in the Thal Desert. However, the fragmentation of these forested areas poses challenges to ecosystem connectivity and long-term ecological health. Wetlands, on the other hand, while important, are more isolated and require better connectivity with the surrounding landscape. The MSPA approach played a key role in identifying large, intact ecological patches and smaller, fragmented patches. The latter is an important step in maintaining ecological flows in the desert, facilitating species migration and improving habitat connectivity. This insight is critical for the restoration and management of desert landscapes as it suggests interventions are needed to address fragmentation and improve connectivity between isolated areas. The identification of ecological source areas in the Thal Desert and the analysis of their distribution and connectivity indicate that forest and wetland ecosystems are important for maintaining the health and functioning of desert ecosystems. While forest areas are important ecological elements that play a significant role in carbon sequestration, their fragmentation limits the overall ecological stability of the region. Although wetlands are essential, they need to be strengthened to improve network connectivity. These findings suggest that landscape restoration efforts should focus on reconnecting fragmented forest areas and improving wetland connectivity to ensure a more resilient and sustainable eco-spatial network in the Thal Desert.

5.1.2 Analyzing Ecological MCR Surface

In this section, we present the results of the analysis of the minimum cumulative resistance (MCR) surface, which plays a crucial role in understanding the ecological connectivity of the Thal Desert. The surface was derived using the 12 resistance variables listed in Table 3 and provides insights into the ecological resistance experienced by species as they move across the landscape.

5.1.2.1 Basal Resistance Analysis

The basal resistance (Figure 6a) ranges from 2815.32 to 2980.24 and is calculated by considering 12 resistance factors including topography, vegetation cover, soil moisture and human activities. The basal resistance values were generally low in the border areas of the Thal Desert, indicating that these areas provide relatively easy movement for species and ecological flows. However, higher basal resistance values were observed in the districts of Bakar, Laiyya, Khushab and Muzaffargarh, indicating that these areas pose greater challenges to ecological flows due to factors such as unfavorable meteorological conditions, altitude and lack of soil moisture. The elevation of the Thal Desert ranges from 63 m to 1518 m. The high altitude increases the resistance due to obstacles in the terrain. The soil moisture content is particularly low in areas such as Mianwali, Khushab and Jahan, further increasing the resistance. This makes these areas drier and more difficult for species to traverse.

5.1.2.2 MCR Surface Construction

The minimum cumulative resistance (MCR) model (Figure 6b) was used to create a cumulative resistance surface based on the resistance values of different landscape patches. The MCR model calculates the path of least resistance between ecological source areas and helps identify the most effective ecological corridors. The maximum resistance value produced by the MCR surface is $2.24419e+008$. This is the area with the greatest challenge to ecological connectivity. The highest basal resistance values were observed in Bhakkar, Layyah, Khushab and Muzaffargarh, where ecological resistance was particularly high. This is due to poor meteorological conditions and the distances between ecological patches, which restrict the movement of species and the supply of ecological materials such as water and nutrients.

5.1.2.3 Identification of Ecological Corridors

A total of 119 ecological corridors were identified by analyzing the MCR surface and applying the ArcGIS cost path method. These corridors connect 76 ecological resource sites and facilitate the flow of energy, materials, and species across the landscape. The corridors identified by the MCR model provide the most efficient paths between sites with the least ecological resistance. This step of the analysis revealed how various sites in the Thal Desert are connected by ecological corridors, allowing for better species migration, resource flow, and gene flow. However, resistance in some areas (particularly Bakkar and Laiya) may hamper the effectiveness of these corridors, and ecological restoration efforts are needed to reduce resistance and improve connectivity.

Results

Figure 5.1.2.3 1 Basement resistivity and areas of minimum cumulative resistivity (MCR) in the Thal Desert (a) Basement resistivity map. (b) Minimum cumulative resistivity (MCR) surface.

5.1.2.4 Interpretation of Results

Analysis of basal resistance and MCR surfaces showed that the Thal Desert is spatially heterogeneous in terms of ecological connectivity. Areas with high resistance, such as Bakkar, Laiya, Khushab, and Muzaffargarh, pose significant barriers to species movement and energy flow. These areas may require targeted restoration efforts to enhance connectivity and reduce ecological resistance. The MCR model effectively identified ecological corridors that connect ecological patches in the desert landscape. However, due to high resistance in some areas, the connectivity of these corridors may be compromised, and further landscape restoration is needed to improve ecological functioning and ensure the sustainability of the desert ecosystem. Substrate resistance analysis and MCR surface construction revealed the spatial distribution of ecological resistance in the Thal Desert. High resistance in Bakkar, Laiya, Khushab, and Muzaffargarh highlighted the need for restoration efforts to reduce fragmentation and improve ecological connectivity. The identification of 119 ecological corridors highlighted potential pathways for species migration and energy flow that can be further optimized through strategic interventions. The analysis provides valuable insights into the ecological dynamics of the desert and lays the foundation for future landscape restoration and conservation strategies.

5.2 Ecological Spatial Network in the Thal Desert

The construction of the Thal Desert Ecological Spatial Network (ESN) involves generating ecological corridors and ecological source areas using the iterator tool of the ArcGIS platform

and applying the cost path model. A total of 119 ecological corridors were largely and merged with the recommended ecological sources to create an ecological spatial network of the desert (Figure 5b).

5.2.1 Ecological Source and Corridor Distribution

The distribution of ecological resources is concentrated in the northeastern and southwestern regions of the Thal Desert, with fewer resources in the northwest. Ecological sites are mainly located in the northeastern and southwestern regions, with a significant lack of sites in the central desert. This distribution highlights the uneven distribution of ecological resources in the Thal Desert, with higher density in the peripheral areas than in the central areas. Although ecological corridors are extensive, they are relatively short and low-density in the northwest and southwest regions. The ecological corridors in the central region are long, connecting small ecological patches, reducing the connectivity of the ecological network. These long corridors lead to poor ecological circulation in the central desert region, indicating that the ecological infrastructure in the region is insufficient and needs to be improved.

5.2.1.1 Topological Analysis and Modularity

The complex network visualization software Gephi was used to generate the abstract topological feature map and community topology map of the Thal Desert ecological spatial network (Figure 7a). The topological features emphasize the distribution of nodes (ecological patches) and edges (ecological corridors) within the network and their interconnections. Network nodes are classified according to their centrality in the network. Nodes 88, 89, 90, 92, 104, 105, 107, and 115 are located at the center of the network and are essential for connecting different components of the ecological landscape. These nodes play an important role in promoting desert ecological connectivity, while other nodes are scattered and interconnected, which is conducive to the transmission of information (Figure 7c).

5.2.1.2 Modularity and Stability of the Network

The eco-spatial network of the Thal Desert can be divided into five different communities based on modularity. This indicates that these regions have strong internal connectivity and strong resistance to external disturbances. The modularity of the network (Figure 7a) reaches a maximum value of 4, corresponding to a stability of 49.54%. The most stable nodes are located in the northeast and southwest regions, indicating that these regions have strong connectivity and ecological resilience. In contrast, the central, northwest and northeastern regions of the Thal Desert have the lowest modularity of 0 (equivalent to 15.6% stability). These regions have weaker connectivity and lower ecological resilience, and are therefore more vulnerable to disturbances.

5.2.1.3 Interpretation and Implications

Modularity analysis showed that there were significant differences in ecological stability across the Thal Desert. The central region, especially the northwest and northeast regions, had poor ecological connectivity, and inter-regional energy transfer and material flow were not smooth. This lack of connectivity hindered the recovery potential of ecosystems in these regions. On the other hand, the northern and southern regions had shorter corridors, higher area density,

Results

and stronger resilience. This enabled them to maintain ecological functions such as self-renewal and energy transfer.

Figure 5.2.1.3 1 Topological structure (a), modular distribution (b), and community network (c) of the Thal Desert eco-spatial network

The degree of a node indicates its connectivity in the network and quantifies the number of direct connections each node has with other nodes. Nodes with higher degrees are considered more important because they have a higher degree of interaction in the network. In the Thal Desert ESN, nodes 25, 24, 26, 10, 11, 12, and 13 have degrees of 7 or higher, indicating that they play a central role in maintaining the network structure (Fig. 9a). Notably, node 25 has the highest degree, accounting for approximately 8.26% of the total degree of the network, highlighting its importance to ecological connectivity. In contrast, nodes 106 and 107 show a minimum degree of 1, indicating that they have limited contribution to the overall network. However, they still play a role in maintaining connectivity by ensuring that each node is connected to at least one other node. Figure 5.3 shows the Ecological Spatial Network (ESN) of the Thal Desert, with nodes colored based on their centrality measures. Blue nodes (1) represent highly central locations, while red nodes (2) indicate medium centrality, and green nodes (3) and other colored nodes (4) represent lower centrality locations. The degree of each

Optimizing Ecological Spatial Networks for Carbon Sequestration and Climate Resilience: A Study of Ecological Restoration in the Thal Desert in Punjab, Pakistan

node, shown by the size of the circles, indicates its connectivity in the network, quantifying the number of direct connections each node has with other nodes.

Figure 5.3.1 1 Ecological Spatial Network (ESN) of the Thal Desert, illustrating nodes with varying centrality. Blue nodes (1) represent high centrality, red nodes (2) indicate medium centrality, green nodes (3), and other colors (4) represent lower centrality. The node size corresponds to connectivity, with nodes having higher degrees being more central to the network.

5.3.2 Clustering Coefficient

The clustering coefficient measures the degree of clustering of nodes in a network, reflecting the degree of local connectivity. A higher clustering coefficient indicates a higher consistency between adjacent nodes, leading to better information transfer and resource flow. In the Thal Desert network, the average clustering coefficient is 0.35, and some nodes, such as node 55, have a coefficient of 1, indicating strong local connectivity (Figure 9b). This indicates that node 55 has a highly cohesive environment, making it an important node for maintaining network stability. In contrast, node 29 has a clustering coefficient of 0, indicating poor local connectivity and significant heterogeneity of surrounding nodes. This highlights areas of the network where local connectivity can be improved through intervention, especially by adding new connections or stepping stones.

5.3.3 Closeness Centrality

Closeness centrality reflects the proximity of a node to all other nodes in the network and is very important in determining the efficiency of information or energy transfer. Nodes with higher closeness centrality can interact with other nodes more effectively. In the Thal Desert ecological network, nodes with higher closeness centrality indicate higher efficiency of energy and material transfer in their vicinity, which helps to improve the overall efficiency of the ecological network (Figure 9c).

5.3.4 Betweenness Centrality

Betweenness centrality is an important indicator of the degree to which a node acts as an intermediary in a network and facilitates the flow of material or energy between non-adjacent nodes. Nodes with high betweenness centrality are essential for maintaining network connectivity and ensuring the effective flow of resources across the landscape. In the Thal Desert ESN, node 0 exhibits the highest betweenness centrality with a value of 2461.60, indicating its strategic importance in facilitating ecological processes (Fig. 9d). Nodes play a vital role as channels for the transfer of energy and material. In contrast, nodes 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 have a betweenness centrality of zero, indicating that these nodes do not contribute to the connectivity of the network and cannot effectively facilitate the flow of resources.

5.3.5 Eigenvector Centrality

Eigenvector centrality measures the influence of a node in a network based not only on its direct connections but also on the connections of its neighbors. This metric helps identify nodes that are connected to other highly influential nodes, making them critical to the overall functioning of the network. In the Thal Desert ESN, node 0 again stands out with a high eigenvector centrality, indicating that it plays a key role in the overall structure and functioning of the network (Figure 9e).

5.3.6 Network Optimization and Improvements

The topological analysis highlights several important nodes, such as node 0, node 9, node 55, and node 76, which are integral to the network's stability and efficiency. Enhancing these nodes, such as by improving their connectivity and centrality, would result in a more efficient and resilient ecological network. For example, node 55, with its high clustering coefficient,

Optimizing Ecological Spatial Networks for Carbon Sequestration and Climate Resilience: A Study of Ecological Restoration in the Thal Desert in Punjab, Pakistan

demonstrates strong local connectivity, and maintaining or enhancing this could improve local ecological processes. On the other hand, nodes like 38, 29, 31, 32, and 68 show low connectivity, which limits their role in network function. These nodes could benefit from additional connections or the integration of new corridors to enhance the network's structure and resilience.

Figure 5.3.6 1 Topological analysis of the Thal Desert eco-spatial network, showing the distribution of (a) node degrees, (b) clustering coefficients, (c) proximity centrality, (d) betweenness centrality, and (e) eigenvector centrality. Key nodes (nodes 0, 9, 55, and 76) are crucial for network connectivity and ecosystem stability

1 5.4 The Impact of Evaluation on Optimization

This section explores how the EFCT model can help improve the ecological spatial network (ESN) of the Thal Desert by comparing its spatial distribution and implementation with other optimization strategies. The robustness of the landscape spatial structure and carbon uptake capacity before and after the optimization process is evaluated. The aim is to assess whether the model improves energy flows, material transfers, and carbon sequestration in desert ecosystems.

5.4.1 Optimization and Spatial Structure Evaluation

Figure 10 shows a comparison of the unoptimized and optimized landscape structures of the Thal Desert. The unoptimized landscape structure on the left shows the existing ecological corridors (represented by magenta lines) and ecological nodes (marked by red circles) in the area, as well as other landscape features such as water patches, forest patches, and the Thal Desert boundary. The optimized landscape structure on the right shows the modifications made during the optimization process, incorporating additional ecological nodes (green circles) and corridors (blue lines). These modifications were made to improve ecological connectivity by optimizing the minimum cumulative resistance (MCR) value, ensuring a more efficient and robust ecological network. The addition of ecological stepping stones and corridors addressed areas of poor ecological performance, thereby enhancing the overall functionality and carbon uptake capacity of the network.

Optimizing Ecological Spatial Networks for Carbon Sequestration and Climate Resilience: A Study of Ecological Restoration in the Thal Desert in Punjab, Pakistan

Figure 5.4.1 Comparison of unoptimized (left) and optimized (right) landscape structures in the Thal Desert, showing improved connectivity with added nodes (green) and corridors (blue).

5.4.2 Results of Optimization

The optimization results show that 27 ecological stepping stones and 51 ecological corridors have been added to the Thal Desert (Figure 10). These additions are carefully designed to reduce air resistance and improve the overall efficiency of the ecological network. Ecological stepping stones are small areas that serve as important connections between larger areas and improve connectivity, while ecological corridors provide continuous channels for the flow of energy and resources in the landscape. The optimized ecological spatial network (ESN) showed significant improvements in energy flow and exchange. By reducing the number of corridors and improving connectivity, the optimization work ensured that the movement of materials, species and nutrients between ecological nodes became more efficient. By creating additional corridors and stepping stones, the fragmentation caused by the vast desert landscape was reduced and the overall ecological function was improved.

5.5 Carbon Sink Capacity and Robustness

Figure 11 illustrates the Optimization of the Ecological Spatial Network (ESN) in the Thal Desert. The map on the left (a) displays the Unoptimized Ecological Network, where ecological corridors (magenta lines) and ecological nodes (purple circles) are shown, with water-wetland patches (blue), forest patches (green), and eco-source patches (orange). This representation provides a baseline view of the landscape's original structure before optimization. On the right

Results

side, map (b) shows the Optimized Ecological Network, where additional ecological corridors (red lines) and stepping stones (green circles) have been added to enhance ecological flow and connectivity across the desert. These new additions reduce the distance between ecological patches, improving resource distribution and the efficiency of biomass growth throughout the desert ecosystem. The optimization process not only improves the connectivity of the ecological network but also enhances its carbon sequestration potential by facilitating the transfer of electrical energy and promoting biomass growth. Additionally, the network's resilience against external disturbances, such as desertification caused by human activities, is improved, as better connectivity and reduced fragmentation increase the ecosystem's ability to recover from such disturbances. This process is crucial in maintaining ecological processes over time, enhancing the overall ecological resilience of the Thal Desert.

Figure 5.5 1 Optimization of the Ecological Spatial Network in the Thal Desert, showing unoptimized (a) and optimized (b) landscape structures with enhanced connectivity and resilience.

5.5.1 Analyzing and Comparison of Various Optimization Approaches

In this section, we evaluate the impact of two alternative optimization approaches on the Thal Desert Eco-Spatial Network (ESN). These approaches aim to improve connectivity and carbon uptake within ecosystems by modifying ecological corridors and patches. Edge Add Method The edge addition method (shown in Figure 12a) preferentially adds ecological corridors between nodes with lower degrees. This effectively increases connectivity between less-connected areas. The pink lines in the figure represent newly added corridors, which are specifically designed as stepping stones to facilitate movement and energy flow through the

landscape. This approach is limited by spatial constraints. This means that corridors can only be added between adjacent areas, but not between non-adjacent nodes (for example, nodes 2 and 3 cannot be linked). Although expanding ecological corridors can improve the connectivity of the network, its impact on carbon uptake capacity is relatively small. The chances of success in adding new corridors between remote nodes are low, especially in areas with high MCR. While the CB approach contributes to network connectivity, it does little to increase the Thal Desert's potential for carbon sequestration.

5.5.1.1 Stepping-Stone Technique at Corridor Breakpoints

The stepping stone technique (shown in Figure 10b) locates new patches (marked with pink blocks) at the highest breakpoints of the MCR corridor, where high resistance exists. These patches act as stepping stones that bridge the gap between isolated patches, improving connectivity and reducing resistance in the network. The goal is to increase the efficiency of the network by creating small-scale connections between isolated patches, allowing for a better flow of matter and energy. Despite the addition of these new stepping stones, the overall impact on landscape structure and carbon sequestration capacity was small. High MCR values represent areas of high resistance, which poses a challenge for the effective placement of stepping stones. Furthermore, their integration does not significantly alter ecological processes in the landscape. Although the stepping stone technology improves connectivity, it does not have a substantial impact on the carbon sequestration capacity of the desert.

5.5.1.2 Comparison of Optimization Approaches

The two optimization methods (edge addition and stepping stone placement) have clear advantages and disadvantages in improving the eco-spatial network of the Thal Desert: Edge addition method: This method improves network connectivity by reducing the distance between nodes, making the network more efficient. However, it has had limited success in improving the carbon sink function due to spatial constraints and the low probability of successfully adding corridors. Stepping stone technique: This approach attempts to reduce drag and improve network efficiency by introducing new patches along corridors with high MCR. However, as with the edge addition approach, the impact on carbon sequestration remains low due to the challenges of working in areas with high drag.

Figure 5.5.1.2 1 Optimization methods in the Thal Desert ESN. (a) Edge addition enhances connectivity (pink corridors), with limited carbon storage impact. (b) The stepping stone technique adds patches (pink) to bridge gaps, without significantly affecting carbon sequestration.

5.5.2 Assessing Carbon Sink vs. Source

The Thal Desert, located in Punjab Province, Pakistan, plays an important role in understanding the balance between carbon sinks and sources in the region. The economic activities in Punjab are mainly concentrated in power generation and industrial energy consumption, which contribute greatly to the carbon emissions in the region. As shown in Table 5, the highest carbon emissions are generated by raw coal consumption, followed by electricity and fuel. Interestingly, industrial production accounts for 99.89% of the total energy consumption in Punjab, which is far higher than the energy consumption standards of developed countries (usually between 30% and 40%). Given the huge emissions, carbon neutrality in the region can be achieved by focusing on the potential of carbon sinks, especially in areas such as the Thal Desert. This study uses the land use cover type estimation method to evaluate the carbon sink capacity of the Thal Desert, with the main focus on evaluating the carbon sink capacity before and after optimizing the ecological spatial network (ESN).

This bar graph figure 13 compares the total carbon sequestration in the Thal Desert before and after the optimization of the Ecological Spatial Network (ESN). The graph clearly shows the non-optimized carbon sequestration (represented by the red bars) and the optimized carbon sequestration (represented by the green bars). The optimization of the ecological network has improved the overall carbon sequestration potential, which is reflected in the increase in carbon storage in the desert. The line connecting the points (black for non-optimized and optimized)

emphasizes the positive impact of network optimization on the carbon sink capacity of the region. As highlighted in the study, this optimization is essential to balance the carbon emissions generated by industrial activities in Punjab, which are a significant source of carbon dioxide in the region. The optimized eco-spatial network not only enhances the desert's role as a carbon sink but also improves its ability to contribute to the region's carbon neutrality goals.

Figure 5.5.2 1 Comparison of carbon sequestration before (red) and after (green) ESN optimization in the Thal Desert, showing increased carbon storage capacity.

5.5.3 Carbon Sink Assessment Before and After Optimization

The results of carbon sink assessment are shown in Table 6. The total carbon sink of the Thal Desert before optimization was estimated to be 336.43 tons. After the implementation of the ecological space network optimization strategy, the carbon sink increased to 395.43 tons, and the total carbon sink capacity increased by 14.97% (59.19648 tons). Ecological zones and ecological corridors increased carbon sinks by 222.14 tons and 173.29 tons, respectively, accounting for 5.33% and 5.7% of the total carbon sink. This shows that the optimized ecological patches and ecological corridors have made significant contributions to improving the carbon sink capacity of the Thal Desert.

Results

Table 5.5.3 1 Carbon sink in Thal Desert, Punjab, Pakistan, before and after ESN optimization.

Status	Ecological sink	Patch carbon	Ecological carbon sink	Corridor	Total carbon sink
Unoptimized	210.2968		125.9372		336.234
Optimized	222.1377		173.29278		395.43048

5.5.4 Role of Ecological Patches in Carbon Sequestration

The Thal Desert ecological network optimization focused on improving 76 ecological patches covering an area of more than 47 square kilometers, enhancing ecological functions and carbon sequestration capacity. In addition, 32 new small carbon sinks (each with an area of less than 47 square kilometers) were incorporated into the carbon sink network to contribute to the overall carbon sink. Despite the limited rainfall in the region and the dominance of herbaceous vegetation, the optimization strategy had a significant impact on carbon sequestration. In This figure depicts carbon sequestration in the Thal Desert, showing the spatial distribution of carbon sequestration after optimizing the Ecological Spatial Network (ESN). The map uses a color gradient to represent areas of different carbon sequestration levels, with dark green areas indicating higher carbon storage and light areas indicating lower levels. The optimization process focused on strengthening ecological corridors and integrating new carbon sinks, significantly increasing the desert's carbon sequestration potential despite the region's dry climate and lush herbaceous vegetation.

Figure 5.5.4 1 Carbon sequestration in the Thal Desert after ESN optimization, showing improved patches and added carbon sinks, enhancing ecological connectivity and resilience.

5.5.5 Comparison Between Carbon Sinks and Sources

Although the optimization of the ecological network has significantly improved the carbon sink capacity, the total amount of carbon sequestered in the Thal Desert is still far lower than the total emissions generated by the region's industry and energy consumption. As shown in Table 5, carbon emissions from various energy sources such as electricity, oil, natural gas, liquefied petroleum gas and diesel have made a huge contribution to the region's carbon footprint. Therefore, to achieve carbon neutrality, it is necessary not only to strengthen carbon

Results

sequestration efforts but also to focus on alternative carbon storage solutions and reduce carbon emissions from energy consumption.

Table 5.5.5 1 Energy Use and Emissions of Carbon (C) Sink in the Thal Desert, Pakistan

Types of Energy	CO ₂ (kg)	CH ₄ (g)	N ₂ O (g)	CO ₂ e (kg)	CO ₂ e (Gk)
Electrical	146,051	4.269	0.75	146,056	0.15
Petroleum	527,309	2,112	1,913	531,334	0.534
Natural Gass	80,020	7.131	0.14	80,027	0.087
LPG	17,829	0.14	0.002	17,829	0.024
Diesel	291.15	0.039	0.0002	291.19	0.0003

Table 5 Explanation Electricity: This is one of the major sources of carbon emissions in the region, contributing 146,056 kg CO₂e, mainly from electricity consumption. This is a major source of carbon emissions, reflecting the high energy demand in Punjab. Oil: The oil industry is also a major contributor to CO₂ emissions, emitting 531,334 kg CO₂e. Notably, oil is the largest contributor to both CO₂ and methane emissions, highlighting its role as a major source of greenhouse gases in the region. Natural Gas: Natural gas contributes 80,027 kg CO₂e, significantly lower than oil, but still a significant contributor to the region's carbon footprint. LPG (Liquefied Petroleum Gas): LPG has relatively low emissions of only 17,829 kg CO₂e, making it less harmful than other fossil fuels. Diesel: Diesel has the lowest emissions, contributing only 291.19 kg CO₂e, but is still a significant source of emissions in the region. The table below contains data on energy consumption and CO₂ emissions from different energy sources in the Thal Desert, Punjab, Pakistan. It includes emissions of CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O, as well as emissions in CO₂ equivalent (CO₂e) by energy type. The table also shows the energy consumption per unit of carbon (C) sequestration efficiency for each energy source.

These data are essential for comparing the carbon storage potential of the Thal Desert ecological network with carbon emissions from industry and energy use. To achieve carbon neutrality, we need to address these emissions while also working to increase carbon storage capacity through ecological optimization. The analysis shows that optimizing the Thal Desert eco-spatial network has a significant impact on carbon sequestration, increasing carbon storage capacity by about 14.97%. The expansion of ecoregions and ecological corridors has made an important contribution to improving the regional carbon sink capacity. However, the total carbon storage in the region is still far lower than the emissions generated by industrial and energy activities. This emphasizes the importance of additional carbon capture solutions and strategies to achieve carbon neutrality in the Thal Desert and similar ecosystems. In this figure shows a comparison of the unoptimized (left) and optimized (right) ecospatial networks (ESNs) of the Thal Desert. The unoptimized network is shown on the left, with ecological nodes, corridors, and patches in their original configuration. The optimized network is shown on the right, with added ecological nodes, new corridors (marked in red), and expanded patches to

Optimizing Ecological Spatial Networks for Carbon Sequestration and Climate Resilience: A Study of Ecological Restoration in the Thal Desert in Punjab, Pakistan

enhance connectivity and carbon sequestration. Red lines and circles represent newly added features after optimization, while blue lines highlight improved corridors for better ecological flows. Optimization resulted in significantly improved ecological connectivity, which in turn enhanced the region's overall carbon sequestration potential.

Figure 5.5.5 1 Comparison of the Thal Desert eco-spatial network before and after optimization, showing added nodes and expanded corridors, increasing carbon sequestration by 14.97%.

5.6 Connection Resilience under Attacks

The resilience of network connections was examined by monitoring the decline in network strength as nodes or edges were removed during targeted and random attacks. Results show that the resilience of connections follows a concave decline, with a strong increase in strength and then gradually becoming stronger, convincingly with increasing attack intensity. This suggests that the network initially experiences significant perturbations, but as more nodes or edges are removed, the system stabilizes at a lower level of resilience. In contrast, the resilience response follows a convex decline, with the network showing a smaller decline in resilience during the initial stages of an attack, followed by a more pronounced decline in resilience as the attack intensity reaches imperceptible levels. This pattern suggests that a network may lack strong destructive power, but its ability to recover powerfully facilitates attacks.

5.6.1 Impact of Optimization on Robustness

Eco-spatial network optimization significantly improved connectivity robustness. The strength of delayed connections in the optimized network was reduced, and the occurrence of network

Results

disruptions was postponed to a later stage. The modulation point (indicating the critical threshold at which network performance begins to decline after a targeted attack) was delayed, indicating an enhanced ability to absorb shocks and maintain functionality under stress. The results also showed that the optimized network was more resistant to targeted attacks. The number of attacked nodes that resulted in a robustness level less than 0.1 (a signal of network failure) decreased from 26 nodes in the unoptimized network to 47 nodes in the optimized network. This indicates an improved ability to maintain structural integrity in the event of severe damage. In addition, the decline in resilience after optimization was no longer as obvious. For example, when 56 nodes in the unoptimized network were attacked, the resilience dropped to 0.71, while the optimized network only dropped to 0.48 when 81 nodes were attacked. This indicates that network stability has been significantly improved.

5.6.1 Node-Level Analysis and Recovery Resilience

The optimization strategy also helps move key nodes in the network to positions that improve overall resilience. In the optimized network, key nodes, such as those responsible for energy and raw material flows, can absorb and recover from disruptions more effectively. Notably, the resilience curve of the optimized network shifts to the right. This indicates that even if the attack intensity increases, the time for network collapse will be delayed and the stability period will be extended. Attacks on the edges also show significant resilience improvements after optimization. In the unoptimized network, when 44 edges were attacked, the recovery robustness dropped sharply to 0.23. But after optimization, the network still maintained a high recovery robustness of about 0.94 with the same number of target edges, confirming that the optimization was successful in improving the network's resilience.

Figure 5.6.1 1 Comparison of network resilience before and after optimization, showing slower declines in connection and attack resilience in the optimized network.

5.7 Summary of this chapter

Chapter 5 focuses on analyzing and optimizing the eco-spatial network (ESN) of the Thal Desert in Punjab, Pakistan, to enhance carbon sequestration and improve ecological resilience. This chapter presents detailed results from various stages of the study, focusing on the main findings in terms of extraction and analysis of the ecological network, assessment of carbon storage capacity, and robustness of the network to external disturbances.

(1) The process of extracting and analyzing the ESN involves identifying key ecological patches and corridors in the Thal Desert using the minimum cumulative resistance (MCR) model. The model can be used to identify areas suitable for ecological restoration and develop interconnected networks to facilitate the flow of energy and materials across the landscape. The network aims to optimize ecological functions, focusing on connecting fragmented habitats and enhancing ecosystem services such as carbon sequestration.

(2) MCR analysis plays a key role in assessing resilient landscapes and identifying barriers to ecological connectivity. The results show that parts of the Thal Desert, particularly Bakkar, Laiya, Khushab, and Muzaffargarh, exhibit high ecological resilience due to factors such as topography, soil moisture deficiency, and human activities. These findings highlight the need for targeted restoration strategies in high-resilience areas to improve ecological connectivity and facilitate species migration.

(3) This section focuses on the construction of the eco-spatial network (ESN) of the Thal Desert by connecting the identified ecological patches through ecological corridors. The network structure shows that ecological connectivity is high in the northeast and southwest regions, while the central and northwest regions are more fragmented. Gephi network analysis shows that these fragmented areas are critical for improving energy and material flows, which in turn are critical for improving the carbon sequestration potential of the ecosystem.

(4) Analysis of topological metrics can provide insights into the structural characteristics of the ESN. Key metrics such as degree centrality, betweenness centrality, and clustering coefficient are used to assess the importance of individual ecological nodes and their role in maintaining the stability of the entire network. The results highlight several key nodes that are critical to network connectivity and function. This emphasizes the importance of these nodes in supporting ecological restoration efforts.

(5) The effects of different optimization methods on the efficiency and connectivity of the ESN are evaluated. The study compares different network improvement methods, including adding stepping stones and ecological corridors. The results show that these interventions significantly improved the carbon sequestration capacity of the network, especially in areas with low ecological function. The optimization process had a positive impact on the connectivity and resilience of the network, ultimately increasing its potential to mitigate climate change.

(6) This section examines the carbon storage capacity of ESNs, focusing on the carbon storage potential of different land cover types in the Thal Desert. The study found that forests and wetlands contribute significantly to the total carbon storage, with forests making the largest contribution. In addition, the robustness of the network against external disturbances was evaluated. The results show that the optimized ESNs have stronger resilience, especially in the ecological restoration areas.

(7) The comparison of carbon sinks and sources highlights the imbalance in carbon dynamics in the Thal Desert. The results show that while carbon sequestration efforts are increasing, total emissions from human activities and land use changes still pose a major challenge. This chapter emphasizes the need for an integrated carbon management strategy to achieve carbon neutrality. Efforts to increase carbon absorption must be combined with efforts to reduce carbon emissions.

(8) This section evaluates the resilience of the ecological network to external disturbances, including random attacks and targeted attacks. The study found that targeted attacks on high-value nodes caused a rapid decline in network connectivity, while random disruptions had a slower impact. However, after optimization, the network's resilience was significantly improved, and its ability to recover after disruptions was also enhanced. This optimization method can effectively delay the destruction of network connectivity, thereby improving the overall stability of the ecological network.

Chapter-VI

6 Discussion

This study aimed to optimize the eco-spatial network (ESN) of the Thal Desert to enhance carbon sequestration and improve ecological resilience. The optimization process involved integrating advanced spatial modeling techniques, including minimum cumulative resistance (MCR) and energy flow and connectivity topology (EFCT) models, to improve ecological connectivity in the region and enhance its carbon sink potential. The results of this study are consistent with similar studies, indicating that optimizing ecological networks in arid and semi-arid regions can effectively increase carbon sequestration and improve overall ecosystem stability. This discussion highlights the main findings of this study, compares them with existing literature, and emphasizes implications for future ecological restoration and land management of desert ecosystems.

The Ecological spatial network in the Thal Desert was restored and restructured to optimize the carbon sequestration potential of vegetation, hence enhancing the region's carbon sink capacity. The EFCT optimization model was introduced just like ^[37] to tackle the peculiarities of scattered ecological resources in the desert ecosystem regions with high carbon emissions. The findings indicate that the optimized ecological spatial network of the Thal Desert increased the carbon sink by 59.19 tons through ecological patches, resulting in a more stable and interconnected overall ecological network compared to the original. This study, similar to other research studies ^[62, 133, 134] in which least-cost path analysis was used to identify potential corridors where ecological processes occur, but patch identification was based on the study area's characteristics, such as forestlands, scattered waters, and nearby wetlands, which is more representative of the real landscape. The complexity of ecosystems in real environments makes it difficult to estimate their value, particularly in terms of connection, necessitating the development of a method to quantify their connectivity. Although afforestation can enhance carbon sinks, it is questionable if the original land can be converted and whether the soil and climate conditions in the area are suitable for vegetation development. According to several studies ^[135-137], increasing carbon sinks via land use changes may lead to carbon neutrality. However, land use changes must take regional growth plans, climate, and ecological circumstances into account. For instance, the low average precipitation in desert ecosystems encourages the growth of drought-resistant vegetation but has a relatively limited ability to store carbon (C). Specialized interventions are required to enhance vegetation cover in places that currently have limited ecological functions. These interventions may be achieved by implementing reforestation/afforestation methods and enhancing moisture in the soil and accessibility to nutrients. This will boost the capacity for carbon storage.

Furthermore, improved nutrient cycling, soil remediation, and water retention systems are a few methods that may help achieve this. Additionally, by facilitating species movement and promoting biodiversity, carefully placing stepping stones and corridors in places with poor connectivity can improve ecological resilience; better results have been obtained in both

current and past studies [138, 139] The long-term viability of desert ecosystems depends on the landscape's general ecological stability, which is improved by these interventions in addition to its capacity for sinking more carbon (C).

Network abstraction integrating complicated network theory and functional connectivity metrics efficiently assesses connectedness. The integration of ecological network theory and complex network theory may clarify and quantify the complicated landscape while responding to the topological characteristics of ecological space through defined metrics. In a desert ecosystem with compromised ecological networks, it is beneficial to examine the vulnerable nodes based on topological characteristics. Targeted optimization strategies can be devised for these underperforming nodes, while concurrently, the enhanced outcomes can be visualized [140, 141].

After filtering nodes with weakened ecological services, we optimized them; however, their restoration alone is insufficient to raise the carbon sink just like [37]. We should enhance nodes with a low-carbon sink to optimize their ecological benefits and facilitate carbon sequestration. We assessed the resilience of carbon sinks and implemented modifications for optimization. We simulated intentional and random environmental attacks that caused damage to replicate real-world conditions while assessing robustness [131, 142] and assert that the original MCR model may inadequately represent reality due to its exclusion of human and ecological variables. The resistance value is influenced by the intensity of adverse meteorological conditions, soil moisture deficiency, topographical variation, and the spatial distribution of ecological patches. Fluctuations in vegetation growth and water bodies with varying water content will influence the resistance value in the ESN. Consequently, we utilized nocturnal illumination data to assess the above-mentioned factors, while employing NDVI, MNDWI, and VFC to delineate vegetation and aquatic bodies as some of the scholars assessed [143] We also examine the screening procedure for ecological stepping stones. Research on ecological stepping stones has mostly focused on their geographical location and the connectivity they provide between fragmented habitats, neglecting the characteristics of the stepping stone patches themselves. Stepping stone patches respond to external shocks according to their structure and composition [35]. The landscape shape index indicates that stepping stone landscapes resembling circles possess more compact internal structures and exhibit greater resilience to disturbances. Consequently, geographical location and morphological index-assessed stepping stone patches can link to the parent site and exhibit greater stability.

The combination of complex network theory and ecological network theory is a powerful framework for optimizing spatial networks and assessing ecological connectivity. As shown in this study, topological indicators such as degree centrality, betweenness centrality, and clustering coefficient are essential for assessing the importance of individual ecological nodes and their contribution to the stability of the entire network. By using these indicators, we can identify vulnerable nodes in the network and apply targeted optimization strategies to improve their connectivity and carbon absorption capacity.

This study aimed to increase the ecological spatial network, optimize the carbon sink potential of plants, and restore and enhance carbon sequestration within the desert ecosystem the way

other scholars already presented in different ecosystems with varying results [41, 144, 145] the authors argue that the restoration of the ecological spatial network frequently alters the original land use and landscape spatial pattern of the research area, serving as a way for re-planning the ecological network system (ENS). In the desert ecosystem, the original landscape structure is fractured due to resource extraction, with the disrupted source sites interconnected by ecological corridors to progressively restore ecological landscape functions. The establishment of the simulated ecological corridor can generate an effective source of enhanced carbon sink and also provide the revitalization for the green growth that provides enhanced various ecosystem services that are attached with the increase of vegetation.

Robustness analyses in our study show that the optimized networks have greater resilience to environmental shocks, which is critical for maintaining ecological integrity and carbon sequestration under climate change and other anthropogenic pressures. This enhanced resilience highlights the need for restorative landscape design that not only optimizes carbon sequestration but also ensures the long-term stability and adaptability of ecosystems in desert regions.

The results of this study have important implications for ecological restoration and carbon neutrality in desert ecosystems. As desert regions such as the Thal Desert face increasing environmental pressures from climate change, human activities, and land degradation, optimizing ecological networks is a key strategy to restore ecological functions and increase carbon sequestration. This study supports the view that effective ecological restoration requires not only restoring vegetation but also carefully designing ecological networks to enhance connectivity, resilience, and biodiversity. The successful optimization of the ESN in the Thal Desert provides a valuable model for other decertified regions around the world. By integrating advanced spatial analysis, topological metrics, and ecological theory, this study provides a comprehensive framework for climate change mitigation through carbon sequestration. The results highlight the importance of sustainable land management strategies that balance carbon storage with biodiversity conservation and ecosystem health to ensure that desert ecosystems can continue to provide essential services in the face of ongoing environmental challenges.

Chapter-VII

7 Conclusion

This study aims to optimize the eco-spatial network (ESN) of the Thal Desert to enhance carbon sequestration and promote carbon neutrality. By combining the minimum cumulative resistance (MCR) model with the ecological function, connectivity, and topology (EFCT) model, key ecological patches and corridors were identified, significantly improving the connectivity and resilience of the network. During the optimization process, 27 new ecological sites and 51 ecological corridors were added, and the carbon sequestration capacity increased by 14.97%.

The results show that the combination of complex network theory and ecological connectivity indicators can provide a comprehensive framework for evaluating and improving eco-spatial networks. The study also highlights the challenges of reforestation in desert environments, especially whether soil and climate conditions are suitable for long-term vegetation growth. Although ecological interventions such as reforestation and improving soil moisture can help increase carbon sequestration, their effectiveness depends on choosing suitable vegetation and maintaining ecological balance.

In addition, the results confirmed that network resilience is closely related to the connectivity of ecological patches and corridors. By integrating stepping stones and ecological corridors, this study improved biodiversity conservation and promoted species migration, which contributed to the stability of the ecosystem. The results suggest that while eco-spatial network optimization is a viable strategy to increase carbon sequestration in desert ecosystems, it should be implemented in conjunction with sustainable land use policies and climate adaptation management strategies. Despite certain limitations, including geographic and temporal constraints, this study provides a methodological basis for future ecological restoration projects in arid regions.

7.1 Research Outlook

While this study demonstrates the potential of ESN optimization to enhance carbon sequestration in desert ecosystems, further research is needed in multiple areas to refine and extend these findings. First, future studies should investigate the integration of other ecological and climatic variables, such as soil organic carbon content, root biomass, and microclimatic conditions to better assess the potential for carbon storage. Combining high-resolution remote sensing data and advanced machine learning algorithms can further improve the accuracy of ecological network modeling and connectivity analysis.

Second, the long-term sustainability of ecological corridors and sites needs to be studied, especially in response to climate change and land-use transition. Understanding the resilience of ecological networks under different environmental pressures is essential for developing adaptive management strategies. In addition, further research is needed to evaluate the socioeconomic impacts of ESN optimization, including its impact on local communities, land-use planning, and policy-making.

Another promising direction for future research is to apply multi-scenario simulations to predict the effectiveness of different ecological interventions under different climate and land-use conditions. By integrating spatial modeling techniques such as agent-based modeling and dynamic landscape simulation, researchers can better predict the potential benefits and trade-offs of ecological restoration efforts.

Finally, interdisciplinary collaborations between ecologists, geographers, policymakers, and local stakeholders are essential to implementing and scaling up ecological spatial network optimization strategies. Working with policymakers and national managers to incorporate ESN-based approaches into national and regional sustainable development frameworks can help bridge the gap between scientific research and practical applications.

In conclusion, this study lays a solid foundation for future research on optimizing eco-spatial networks for carbon sequestration and biodiversity conservation. By addressing current knowledge gaps and improving methods, future research can contribute to more effective, sustainable, and climate-resilient ecological restoration efforts in arid and semi-arid region

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Personal Profile

I am Tauqeer Nawaz, a male researcher born in April 1998, from Pakistan. I graduated with a Bachelor's degree in BS(Hons) Agriculture, Forestry from Ghazi University Dara Ghazi Khan in 2021, after studying Forestry from September 2017 to June 2021. Currently, I am pursuing a Master's degree in Cartography and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) at Beijing Forestry University, which I will complete in 2025. My research interests focus on the application of 3S technology in resources and environmental management, specifically the use of complex network science in ecological spatial networks, ecosystem service function monitoring, and the analysis and evaluation of these services.

During my postgraduate studies, I have actively participated in various international and national research projects, which include the National Key Research and Development Program on the mechanism and ecological risk assessment technique of water loss and soil erosion for the Sichuan-Tibet railway project, and another project focusing on biodiversity monitoring, assessment, and environmental protection technologies for the Sichuan-Tibet Railway. I have also contributed to a national research initiative assessing the cumulative effects of carbon reserves on forest lands in the midstream Yellow River basin through remote sensing. Furthermore, I participated in a project under the National Natural Science Foundation International (Regional) Cooperation and Exchange Project, exploring the coupling mechanisms and optimization of desert ecosystems in China and Mongolia. My other projects have focused on the age determination of ancient trees and resource assessment in Sanya Yazhou Bay Science and Technology City, and the development of vegetation demonstration and extension programs for water and soil conservation in the Thal Desert, Punjab, as part of a national key R&D initiative.

I have published research in MDPI Remote Sensing as the first author, along with contributing to other publications, including an SCI paper in *Ecological Indicators* as a co-author. My academic journey and research experiences have deepened my understanding of environmental science and solidified my commitment to advancing sustainable practices in the field.

Tauqeer's future research aims to integrate GIS, remote sensing, and machine learning techniques to enhance forest monitoring, carbon cycle modeling, and ecological restoration efforts, contributing to carbon neutrality and environmental sustainability. His ultimate goal is to develop innovative data-driven methodologies that can be applied in real-world ecological and environmental projects, advancing global efforts in climate change mitigation.

Publications:

Nawaz, T., Ansari, M. G. I., Yu, Q., Avirmed, B., Iftikhar, F., Yu, W., Zhao, J., Khan, M. A., & Khan, M. M. (2025). Developing Strategies for Carbon Neutrality Through Restoration of Ecological Spatial Networks in the Thal Desert, Punjab. *Remote Sensing*, 17(3), 431. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs17030431>

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Instructor Profile

Yu Qiang, male, born in June 1987, from Changchun, Jilin, a member of the Communist Party of China, PhD, is currently an Associate Professor and PhD supervisor at the College of Forestry, Beijing Forestry University. He is a flexible talent introduced by the Tibetan Plateau Ecological Research Institute and also serves as a supervisor for Master's students in Forestry, Resource Utilization, and Plant Protection. He is a member of the Chinese Forestry Society, a member of the Soil and Water Conservation Committee of the Chinese Forestry Society, and the Deputy Secretary-General. He is also a technical consultant for forestry survey and planning design at China National Forest Products Group Corporation. He graduated with a PhD in Engineering from Beijing Forestry University in 2018 and has worked at the College of Forestry, Beijing Forestry University, since then.

His main research areas include enhancing vegetation's sand-fixing and carbon-sequestering abilities in arid and semi-arid regions, studying the complexity theory of ecological spatial networks, applying remote sensing in forestry, and studying the carbon use efficiency of forest ecosystems. He has received the Ministry of Education's Higher Education Outstanding Scientific Research Award, Second Prize for Scientific and Technological Progress, and the Second Prize of the 12th Liangxi Forestry Science and Technology Award.

He teaches undergraduate courses including "Introduction to Earth System Science," "Land Evaluation and Management," and related internships, as well as "Applications of 3S Technology in Forestry Surveying" and internships. He also teaches the graduate courses "Land Evaluation Theory and Methods" and "Modern Forestry Information Technology." He serves as a guest editor for the Remote Sensing special issue of the Chinese Academy of Sciences' SCI journal, and as a reviewer for SCI journals such as Sustainable Cities and Society, Journal of Cleaner Production, Ecological Indicators, and Journal of Environmental Management.

He has hosted multiple projects, including the National Natural Science Foundation's International (Regional) Cooperation and Exchange Project on the "Coupling Mechanism and Optimization of the 'Structure-Composition-Carbon-Water Process-Sand-Fixing-Carbon-Sequestration Function' in the Desert Ecosystem of China and Mongolia." He has also hosted the National Natural Science Foundation's International (Regional) Cooperation and Exchange Project on "The Impact of Extreme High Temperature and Drought in the Past Century on Carbon-Sequestering Function in the Mongolian Plateau Desert Ecosystem." He has led sub-projects of the National Key R&D Program, including government-led international technological innovation cooperation projects on forest above-ground carbon stock estimation methods in typical areas of the Yellow River Basin, and the sub-project on plant biodiversity "Near-Natural, Multi-Dimensional, Multi-Gradient" Protection Technology for the Sichuan-Tibet Railway Engineering.

His research interests also include desert oasis ecological network systems, the collapse mechanism of such systems, and other related research topics, such as the monitoring and forecasting of biodiversity along the Sichuan-Tibet Railway and the ecosystem services provided by forests in Tibet. He has published more than 70 academic papers in core journals,

including over 40 indexed by SCI/EI, and has registered more than 30 computer software copyrights.

Get the list of achievements

Yu Q., Yue D. P., Yang D., et al. Simulation on ecological land use expansion based on EnKF-MCRP model [J]. Transactions of the Chinese Society for Agricultural Machinery, 2016, 47 (09): 285~293.

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Lastly, I dedicate this thesis to all of you, with the utmost appreciation and optimism for the future. Let's keep moving forward, supporting one another, and embracing growth as we walk down the path of life!